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Red-Giant Stars
With
Low Period Spacings

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Rote Riesensterne Mit Geringen Periodenabständen:

Die Asteroseismologie ist eine Methode, um mehr über die innere Struktur von Sternen zu erfahren, statt nur die Oberfläche zu untersuchen. Die Vielzahl von Sternen, die von Teleskopen wie *Kepler* beobachtet wurde, ermöglicht es, auch Sterne in kurzlebigen Entwicklungsstadien oder in seltenen physikalischen Bedingungen zu entdecken.

Eine Gruppe solcher Sterne wurde als rote Haufensterne klassifiziert, jedoch weisen die Oszillationen der gefundenen Sterne geringere Periodenabstände auf als für rote Haufensterne erwartet. Diese Gruppe besteht aus 63 Sternen mit Periodenabständen geringer als 160 s.

Um mehr über diese Sterne zu erfahren und herauszufinden, welcher physikalische Mechanismus für ihre besonderen Parameter verantwortlich sein könnte, habe ich eine Referenzgruppe typischer Sterne des roten Haufens und des roten Riesenastus zusammengestellt. Anschließend habe ich die Parameter der Referenzgruppe und der Sterne mit geringen Periodenabständen auf Unterschiede und Gemeinsamkeiten untersucht.

Abgesehen von ihren geringen Periodenabständen ist das auffälligste Merkmal dieser untypischen Sterne ihre geringe Masse, ein Merkmal, das stark auf einen Massenverlust hindeutet. Außerdem habe ich magnetische Felder, die Rotation des Sterns und den Helium-Blitz als mögliche Erklärungen in Betracht gezogen. Weitere Analysen sind erforderlich, um die Hypothese des Massenverlusts zu verifizieren. Diese Arbeit ist jedoch ein wichtiger erster Schritt zum Verständnis dieser untypischen Sterne mit geringen Periodenabständen.

Red-Giant Stars With Low Period Spacings:

The ability of studying the interior structure of stars makes asteroseismology a powerful method to learn more about stars. Additionally, the large amount of data provided by space telescopes like *Kepler* makes it possible to observe stars in short evolutionary stages or with rare physical conditions.

one such group of atypical stars is those classified as red clump stars but with period spacings lower than expected for red clump stars. This group of stars consists of 63 stars with observed period spacings less than 160 s.

To learn more about these stars and the physical mechanism causing their peculiar asteroseismic parameters, I assembled a reference set including typical red clump and red giant branch stars. I then examined the differences and similarities between the reference set and the set with low period spacings.

The most striking characteristic of these stars, apart from their low period spacing, is their low mass, suggesting mass loss may have occurred. I also considered the possibilities of magnetic activity, stellar rotation and the star undergoing the helium flash.

Further research is needed to verify the hypothesis of mass loss. This work can be considered a first stepping stone to understand the physics of these peculiar stars with low period spacings.

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1 Introduction

Asteroseismology provides the opportunity to "look into" instead of only "look at" stars. The oscillations travelling through the star convey information about the interior structure and physical conditions inside the star.

Thanks to space-based missions like *Kepler* (Borucki et al., 2009), a wealth of data became accessible. Over the years, large ensemble studies were performed (e.g., Hekker et al., 2011b; Yu et al., 2016, 2018), different methods were developed to determine the evolutionary state of the stars (e.g., Kallinger et al., 2012; Elsworth et al., 2017; Hekker et al., 2017), and detailed studies of stars gave insights into their interior structure and conditions, like for example the core rotation (e.g., Beck et al., 2012), or the depth of the helium second-ionization zone (e.g., Miglio et al., 2010). With observations of tens of thousands of stars as provided by *Kepler*, it is expected that it becomes possible to not only find typical stars, but also detect stars in rare physical conditions or short-lived evolutionary states.

Figure 1.1: This figure shows a star with low period spacing in the top panel, and a typical red clump star in the lower panel. The asteroseismic parameters are indicated in the upper left corner of each panel.

Such a sample of stars with peculiar asteroseismic parameters was mentioned by Elsworth et al. (2019). They analysed thousands of red-giant stars to classify their evolutionary states. In their analysis, they noted stars where the classification was difficult due to the peculiar asteroseismic properties of the stars. Among them is the group of stars with suppressed dipole modes, which was also discussed by Mosser et al. (2012a); García et al. (2014b); Fuller et al. (2015). Another sample of stars difficult to classify showed low masses and lacked a clear structure in the $l = 1$ modes. Moreover, the $l = 2$ modes of these stars were described to be difficult to identify. One of the stars given as an example is KIC 9508595.

This star is also included in the sample of Elsworth, Braun, and Hekker (in preparation). They described a sample of stars which resemble red clump stars, but have period spacings lower than expected. Figure 1.1 shows KIC 9508595 compared to KIC 9718024, which is a red clump star with a similar large frequency separation. The radial and quadrupole modes are indicated with numbers according to their spherical degree (0, 2). While the large frequency spacing is similar for both stars, KIC 9508595 has a significantly lower period spacing. The oscillation spectrum of KIC 9508595 looks more "messy" than the red clump star with typical asteroseismic values. As already pointed out by Elsworth et al. (2019), the quadrupole modes of KIC 9508595 are more difficult to identify.

In this thesis, I study the stellar parameters of such peculiar stars to better understand the underlying physics causing the low period spacings. I describe the stellar evolution theory and stellar oscillations in Chapters 2 and 3, respectively. After discussing the data selection in Chapter 4, I explore different reasons and explanations for the peculiar parameters of these stars in Chapter 5. The analysis tools and results are described in Chapters 6 and 7, before ending this thesis with discussing the interpretation of the results in Chapter 8, a summary of the conclusions in Chapter 9, and an outlook in Chapter 10.

2 Stellar Evolution Theory

The evolution of stars is a very extensive topic. This thesis concentrates on evolved stars in the mass range where they develop a degenerate core after the main-sequence. Therefore, this chapter mainly addresses the evolution of low mass stars, with a focus on evolved stars, namely the stars in the red giant branch (RGB) and the red clump (RC).

Figure 2.1 shows the schematic evolution of a star with a mass of $1 M_{\odot}$. I calculated this model for a course work about stellar evolution with the stellar evolution code MESA (Paxton et al., 2011, 2013, 2015, 2018, 2019). The evolution of higher mass ($M_{\star} \sim 2 - 10 M_{\odot}$) and lower mass ($M_{\star} \lesssim 2 M_{\odot}$) stars differ significantly. First, I will describe the evolution of a lower mass star. I will briefly outline the differences to a higher mass star afterwards.

For the most time of a star's life, the dominant mechanism of energy generation is core-hydrogen (H) burning. The region in the Hertzsprung-Russell (HR) diagram where those stars are located is called main-sequence (MS; Figure 2.1, black curve). For a star with a mass of $1 M_{\odot}$, the stable phase of H-burning lasts about 10 Gyr, until the star converted most of the hydrogen in its core to helium (He).

After hydrogen depletion in the core, the star evolves away from the MS. During the following subgiant phase and on the red giant branch (RGB) the main energy production mechanism is shell-H burning (Figure 2.1, blue curve). These stars have a small radiative core, and an outer convection zone that covers most of the remainder of the star. The RGB closely follows the Hayashi-line of fully convective stars, because of the extensive convective region of RGB stars. On the RGB, the properties of the star are mainly determined by the degenerate He-core. Two stars with the same core-mass but different total stellar masses will have the same luminosity in this evolutionary state. The mass of the He-core increases with time as a consequence of the H-shell burning. The increase of core mass has a direct impact on the surface properties of the star. It causes the radius and luminosity to increase. It also causes the temperature in the interior to rise (see Figure 2.1, right panel).

At the tip of the RGB the star has a core mass of approximately $0.48 M_{\odot}$ and a core temperature of about 10^8 K, high enough to ignite He. Since the pressure of the degenerate matter does not depend on the temperature, the core does not expand if the temperature increases. A coupling of temperature and pressure would enable a stable, calm burning of He. Instead, the ignition happens in a run-away reaction.

Neutrino cooling becomes important in this regime. The neutrinos carry away energy from the centre, thus, the highest temperature is not present in the centre but instead in a shell around it. It is predicted that the first He-flash happens in

Figure 2.1: The figure shows the evolution of a $1 M_\odot$ star, calculated with the stellar evolution code MESA. The left panel shows the location of the star in the HR diagram at different evolutionary stages, starting at the zero-age-main-sequence (ZAMS), which is shown for a range of stellar masses (dotted line). After the MS (black), the star evolves towards He ignition (blue), and to the RC after core-He burning started (orange). The dashed lines in the left panel indicate the stellar radius. The right panel shows the corresponding core properties, the dashed line indicates the transition between degenerate and non-degenerate matter.

this shell of maximum temperature. Moving inwards, subsequent He-flashes happen and the rise of temperature lifts eventually the degeneracy of the matter (see Figure 2.1, right panel) and the star starts to burn He in a calm, stable manner.

The luminosity of the star decreases during this very short-lived phase and the final state of the star is in the so-called red clump (RC; Figure 2.1, orange curve) where the primary source of energy is due to core-He burning. A star with a mass of $1 M_\odot$ remains in this state for about 100 Myr, a relatively long time. A central convection zone develops. The luminosity of stars in this evolutionary stage is to a large extent determined by the core mass, thus, stars undergoing a He-flash are located in a similar part of the HR diagram. The effective temperature varies slightly depending on the total mass and the composition of the star.

A higher mass star ($M_\star \sim 2 - 10 M_\odot$) contracts on a Kelvin-Helmholtz-timescale after the MS. The core region heats up, until H-shell burning around the He-core is ignited. Like for lower mass stars, the luminosity and core temperature of the star increases. During the evolutionary phase of the RGB, lower and higher mass stars are located in the same region of the HR diagram. The He-core is not degenerate for higher mass stars. Thus, the onset of core-He burning happens in a quiet manner,

different from the He-flash expected for low mass stars. These stars, which do not ignite He under degenerate conditions evolve to the so-called secondary clump.

Distinguishing core-He burning and RGB stars is no trivial task, since their surface properties are very similar. The region they populate in the HR diagram overlaps. However, their interior structures are significantly different from each other. RGB stars have a convective envelope, and have a radiative region in the interior, which reaches down to the core. Core-He burning stars also have a convective envelope, and a radiative region in the interior. However, the large energy flow due to the He-burning in the core induces a convective region in the core. Asteroseismology provides a way to study the interior structure and gives the opportunity to untangle those populations (see Chapter 3).

A more detailed and complete description can be found in the review paper of Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard (2017) and the book of Kippenhahn et al. (2013).

3 Asteroseismology of Solar-Like Oscillators

3.1 Theory

Oscillations in stars are an important way to study their internal structures. Stellar oscillations transport information about the stellar structure to the surface, thus, they open a window into the star. Stellar oscillations can be observed in stars covering a wide range of stellar evolutionary stages, luminosities and temperatures (Kurtz, 2022). The oscillations differ in timescale and driving mechanism. Here, I concentrate on solar-like oscillations, which are excited by stochastic driving. This kind of oscillation is expected in every star with a convective outer layer. A part of the convective energy is transferred to excite global oscillation modes (Goldreich and Keeley, 1977; Goldreich and Kumar, 1988; Belkacem et al., 2008).

3.1.1 Brief Description of the Derivation of the Equations of Solar-like Oscillations

The first step to derive the equations to describe the pattern in the Fourier transformed light curve of a star is a linear perturbation analysis of the basic stellar structure equations. The required equations are the conservation of mass, conservation of momentum and the equation describing heat transport, supplemented by the Poisson equation. Spherical harmonics are used to rewrite the equations and calculate the eigenvalues, thus, the frequencies of the standing waves. This leaves us with a set of three equations and the respective boundary conditions. Every solution of this set of equations is characterised by three numbers: The radial order n gives the number of nodes in radial direction, the spherical degree l gives the number of nodal lines on the surface, and the azimuthal order m , describes the the number of nodal lines crossing the equator.

However, determining the properties of the stellar oscillations from those equations is not straight forward. Two assumptions greatly simplify the treatment of those equations. From the spherical harmonic expansion of the perturbation of the gravitational potential, one can see that this perturbation can be ignored for modes with large values for the radial order n or spherical degree l . This approximation is called Cowling approximation. The case of modes with large values for n is what is mainly important for asteroseismology. Ignoring the perturbation of the gravitational potential reduces the set of three equations by one, and simplifies the others.

Another simplification which is valid for large values of n is the assumption that

the eigenfunctions vary more rapidly than the equilibrium quantities. This means, one can neglect terms containing the inverse of the pressure scale height. The remaining two equations can be summarised in a single, second-order differential equation for the displacement eigenfunction in radial direction ξ_r :

$$\frac{d^2 \xi_r}{dr^2} = -\frac{\omega^2}{c_s^2} \left(\frac{N^2}{\omega^2} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{S_l^2}{\omega^2} - 1 \right) \xi_r. \quad (3.1)$$

In this equation, the sound speed is denoted as $c_s = \sqrt{\Gamma_1 P / \rho}$, which depends on the density ρ , the pressure P and the adiabatic index Γ_1 . The Lamb frequency S_l is defined as

$$S_l^2 = \frac{l(l+1)c_s^2}{r^2}, \quad (3.2)$$

for a given spherical degree l and the radial coordinate r . The Brunt-Väisälä frequency or buoyancy frequency N is defined as

$$N^2 = g \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma_1 P} \frac{dP}{dr} - \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dr} \right), \quad (3.3)$$

with the surface gravity g of the star. The Brunt-Väisälä frequency describes the frequency of an oscillating fluid element after it was perturbed from its equilibrium position.

In order to have an oscillating solution of the form $\exp(-i\omega t)$, the frequency ω has to be a real number. This is satisfied if a) $\omega^2 > S_l^2$ and $\omega^2 > N^2$, or b) $\omega^2 < S_l^2$ and $\omega^2 < N^2$. These conditions set the boundaries of the cavities where the pressure modes (p modes, Section 3.1.2), and gravity modes (g modes, Section 3.1.3) can propagate, respectively. Further analysis of the regimes where conditions a) and b) are fulfilled give insights into the properties of the p and g modes. The oscillations are damped in the region where neither conditions a) nor b) are fulfilled. This zone is called evanescent zone. The extent of this zone changes during the life of a star and has significant impact on the modes we observe.

For a more thorough derivation of the equations of solar-like oscillations, see Chapter 3 in the book of Basu and Chaplin (2017).

3.1.2 Pressure Modes

Pressure modes, also called p modes, are standing acoustic modes where pressure acts as the restoring force. The propagation region of p modes is in the outer regions of the star, where condition a) $\omega^2 > S_l^2, N^2$ is fulfilled. The region is confined by the surface of the star and the Lamb frequency (Equation 3.2). The typical frequency range where p modes can be detected is the region around the frequency of maximum oscillation power ν_{\max} . For main-sequence stars, ν_{\max} has values of the order of a few mHz. When a star evolves on the RGB, ν_{\max} decreases to frequencies in the sub-mHz to μ Hz regime. During this evolution, the radius of the star increases, which increases the typical period of the oscillations (Hekker, 2013).

ν_{\max} is empirically related to the acoustic cut-off frequency ν_{ac} . For the approximation of an isothermal sphere, ν_{ac} is proportional to the adiabatic sound speed c_s over the pressure scale height H_P . c_s and H_P can be related to the effective temperature T_{eff} and the surface gravity g . H_P is proportional to the ratio of the effective temperature T_{eff} and the surface gravity g . c_s is proportional to $\sqrt{T_{\text{eff}}}$ if adiabaticity and the ideal gas law are assumed (Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2017).

In summary, this links ν_{\max} to the effective temperature and the surface gravity:

$$\nu_{\max} \propto \nu_{\text{ac}} \propto \frac{c_s}{H_P} \propto \frac{g}{\sqrt{T_{\text{eff}}}}. \quad (3.4)$$

Figure 3.1 shows the Fourier spectrum of a star and the pattern from the oscillations. From the asymptotic analysis of the oscillations, a theoretical description of this pattern can be derived. The frequency $\nu_{n,l}$ of an oscillation, with radial order n , and spherical degree l , can be described by

$$\nu_{n,l} \approx \Delta\nu \left(n + \frac{l}{2} + \epsilon_p \right) - d_{n,l}, \quad (3.5)$$

where ϵ_p denotes an offset of the pattern, $\Delta\nu$ denotes the large frequency separation, and $d_{n,l}$ is a correction term.

The large frequency separation is defined as the separation between two modes of the same spherical degree l and consecutive radial order n . $\Delta\nu$ is proportional to the inverse of the sound travel time through the stellar diameter, thus

$$\Delta\nu = \nu_{n,l} - \nu_{n+1,l} = \left(2 \int \frac{dr}{c_s} \right)^{-1} \propto \sqrt{\bar{\rho}}. \quad (3.6)$$

$\Delta\nu$ can be used to slice the power spectrum, and stack the segments to obtain an échelle diagram, as seen in the lower panel of Figure 3.1. In such a diagram, all modes of the same spherical degree lie in one vertical ridge and the identification can be easier.

Towards the surface, the oscillations become difficult to model due to the ongoing convection. The oscillations also become non-adiabatic, further complicating the modelling. This causes an offset between modelled and measured frequencies, which is called the surface effect.

3.1.3 Gravity Modes

A second kind of wave occurring in stars are gravity modes or g modes. Buoyancy acts as restoring force. The Brunt-Väisälä frequency, as defined in Equation 3.3, limits the cavity of the g modes to the interior radiative regions of the star. Further analysis of Equation 3.1 in the regime where the set of conditions b) $\omega^2 < S_l^2, N^2$ is fulfilled shows that g modes are separated equally in period. This separation can be described by

$$\Delta\Pi_l = \frac{2\pi^2}{\sqrt{l(l+1)}} \left(\int_{r_1}^{r_2} N \frac{dr}{r} \right)^{-1} \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3.1: The upper panel shows the regular pattern of the oscillations from the RGB star KIC 7602732. The numbers indicate the spherical degree of the modes. The $l = 1$ modes have clearly mixed mode character, which can be seen by the several peaks around the nominal p-modes. Thus, instead of a single peak merely the region of the location of the several $l = 1$ modes is marked in the upper panel. The lower panel shows an échelle diagram for this star.

where r_1 and r_2 give the lower and upper boundary of the radiative region.

G modes are difficult to observe directly, since their propagation region is confined by the Brunt-Väisälä frequency, and therefore, does not reach to the surface. However, in more evolved stars, the increasing density of the core causes the Brunt-Väisälä frequency to increase. Due to the increasing frequencies of g modes and the decreasing frequencies of p modes they couple as the star ages. This makes it possible to observe g modes as part of so-called mixed modes, as described in the next section.

One strong structural difference between RC and RGB stars is the convective

zone in the inner region of RC stars. This convective zone decreases the size of the radiative region where g modes can propagate. A smaller radiative region means that the period spacing is larger, according to Equation 3.7. This difference was discussed for example by Bedding et al. (2011), and can be used to distinguish between these stellar evolutionary stages which are difficult to disentangle from their surface properties.

3.1.4 Mixed Modes

As the star evolves, the evanescent zone gets smaller, and the frequencies of the p and g modes approach each other. If the evanescent zone is narrow enough, the oscillations couple with each other. This can be described by a system of two coupled oscillators (see Hekker and Mazumdar, 2014). If the coupling constant is large compared to the frequency difference of the two oscillations, an avoided crossing is happening. The two waves avoid the common frequency and are shifted in frequency. Such waves have p mode as well as g mode character, which makes them a great tool for probing the stellar interior. In red giant stars, all oscillation modes, except the radial modes ($l = 0$), have mixed mode character. Because of the high density of g modes in red giant stars, several g modes couple to one p mode. This can be seen in Figure 3.1, where several peaks can be seen around the nominal dipole modes ($l = 1$). The frequency shift of the avoided crossings disturbs the g modes' regular pattern in period.

Figure 3.2 shows the period spacing of consecutive mixed modes $\Pi_{n,l} - \Pi_{n+1,l}$ for the parameters of an example RC star. I calculated the period spacings according to an expression derived by Mosser et al. (2012b). The coupling increases from the bottom panel to the top, all other parameters are the same for all panels. The parameters are given in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Stellar Parameters of KIC 7103297

Parameters	Value
ES	RC
T_{eff} [K]	4760 ± 80
$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	4.293 ± 0.004
ν_{max} [μHz]	38.64 ± 0.25
$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	306
ϵ_g	0.0
ϵ_p	0.977 ± 0.008
α	0.0155 ± 0.0014

The coupling of the modes is stronger for a more narrow evanescent zone and for modes which have more similar frequencies. Thus, modes which are close to a nominal p mode are shifted by a larger amount than modes which are farther

away. The decreased period spacings around the nominal p mode can be seen by the pronounced dips in Figure 3.2, which appear regularly in frequency. The modes farther away from the nominal p modes are more g dominated, and the period spacing resembles the one of pure g modes more closely (Hekker and Mazumdar, 2014).

Figure 3.2: The theoretical description of Mosser et al. (2012b) of the mixed mode period spacing was used to calculate the period spacing. I used the stellar parameters of KIC 7103297 and only varied the coupling strengths.

The dips seen in Figure 3.2 are closely related to the relative contribution of the mode inertia from the inner regions of the star, thus from the g cavity. Mosser et al. (2015) found that the period spacing of consecutive mixed modes $\Pi_{n,l} - \Pi_{n+1,l}$ is related to the asymptotic period spacing $\Delta\Pi_l$ by

$$\Pi_{n,l} - \Pi_{n+1,l} = \zeta \Delta\Pi_l, \quad (3.8)$$

where ζ denotes the fractional contribution of the g cavity to the mode inertia. This can be used to define a parameter transformation to obtain the stretched period τ according to

$$d\tau = \frac{1}{\zeta} \frac{d\nu}{\nu^2}. \quad (3.9)$$

The mixed modes are spaced regularly in period, with a period spacing of $\Delta\Pi_l$ if they are expressed in terms of τ . Thus, τ can be used to obtain ΔP_{i_l} if one applies an iterative procedure. A more detailed derivation of ζ and τ can be found in Mosser et al. (2015) and Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard (2017).

The different panels of Figure 3.2 show the effect of the coupling. A stronger coupling increases the influence of g modes on the modes close to the nominal p mode, thus, the dip is less pronounced. The influence of the g modes brings the period spacing closer to $\Delta\Pi_1$. The stronger coupling also increases the influence of the p modes on the modes which are g dominated and have period spacings close to $\Delta\Pi_1$. The difference between $\Delta\Pi_1$ and the period spacing of those modes becomes larger for increasing coupling, due to the stronger influence of the p modes.

It is predicted (Montalbán et al., 2013) that the coupling between p and g modes is stronger for RC stars than for stars on the RGB.

3.1.5 Rotation

If the maximum centrifugal force at the stellar surface is much smaller than the gravitational force, a star is considered to rotate slowly. For slowly rotating stars, second order effects can be neglected and a perturbative analysis can be performed to gain insights into the effects of rotation on the oscillations. However, this approach is only applicable to oscillations with frequencies much larger than the rotation frequency of the star.

The rotation breaks the spherical symmetry of the star, causing the oscillation frequencies to become m dependent. Each mode with spherical degree l splits up into $2l+1$ modes, having azimuthal orders $m = -l, -l+1, \dots, +l$. The rotational splitting is proportional to m . If the wave travels in the direction of rotation (prograde), the frequency of the mode increases, while it decreases for a retrograde wave.

See Chapter 3.5 of Basu and Chaplin (2017), and Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard (2017) for a mathematical derivation of the effects of rotation on the frequencies of the modes. For a discussion about the effects coming into play for more rapidly rotating stars see Section 5.4

3.2 Observations

After discussing the theory behind the observed oscillations in the previous section, the main characteristics of the data used in this work are outlined here.

Space-based observations posed a major breakthrough in the study of asteroseismology and exoplanets. The shortcomings of ground-based observations such as for example limitations due to the day-night cycle could be overcome by telescopes such as CoRoT (Auvergne et al., 2009) and *Kepler* (Borucki et al., 2010).

The primary goal of the *Kepler* satellite was to study earth-like exoplanets near their habitable zone. However, the continuous observations of stars needed for the

study of exoplanets is also well suited to be analysed with respect to stellar oscillations. The *Kepler* satellite took photometric data over the course of 3.5 years. Two observation modes defined by their cadence, which means the time step between two measurements, were possible: The long cadence took a measurement approximately every 30 min and the short cadence took a measurement every minute.

The total time span of the observations T and the cadence or interval at which data were taken Δt are two important characteristics of a timeseries. The duration of the observation determines the frequency resolution which can be achieved in the Fourier spectrum $\delta\nu = 1/T$. The Nyquist frequency ν_{Nq} is the largest frequency where information of the star can be obtained safely (Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2017), and is determined by the cadence. For evenly spaced data, it is defined as the frequency where two data points are obtained in one oscillation period:

$$\nu_{\text{Nq}} = \frac{1}{2\Delta t}. \quad (3.10)$$

Thus, the long cadence of approximately 30 min is suitable to study stars with oscillation periods larger than 1 hour, or frequencies less than 0.27 mHz. Red giant stars with typical frequencies in the sub-mHz to μHz regime are within this threshold, and thus, can be studied with *Kepler* long cadence data. An example of such data is shown in Figure 3.3, upper panel. The timeseries data are from the RGB star KIC 7602732, and are an example of timeseries data without any large gaps.

Regular gaps in the light curve can cause alias frequencies in the power spectrum, which occur at frequencies of $n\frac{1}{T_{\text{gap}}}$ where n is an integer number and T_{gap} denotes the typical time span between two gaps (Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2017). A very clear example of this effect can be seen when considering ground-based observations. The power spectrum calculated based on the data of one ground-based observation site has strong side lobes, or alias frequencies because of the day-night cycle in the observations. Bradley (2021) clearly demonstrates the improvement of the data if two observation sites of opposite sides of the Earth are used.

The day-night cycle does not impact space-based telescopes, nevertheless, gaps in the light curve are common, often caused by operational procedures like data downloads. Spacecraft manoeuvring can also cause breaks in the observations. For example, the *Kepler* telescope was rotated by 90° approximately every three months to control the orientation of the spacecraft with respect to the Sun, and keep its solar panels illuminated. The observation can further be interrupted by unexpected events as for example problems with the onboard electronics after a cosmic ray (García et al., 2011). Moreover, a broken CCD module of the *Kepler* telescope caused large gaps in the timeseries of affected stars. Thus, gaps should be taken into account when assessing the data quality.

Figure 3.3: The upper panel shows the timeseries data of the RGB star KIC 7602732. In the lower panel, the Fourier transformation of the timeseries data is shown. The individual parts of the background are overplotted. The oscillations were accounted for by including a Gaussian in the full model. The background was fitted with the software TACO (see Chapter 6.1, Hekker et al. in preparation).

3.2.1 Background

Convection does not only excite the oscillation modes, it also induces a background signal. This signal mostly consists of granulation which is the visible pattern of the convection, rotation, and activity features such as spots and flares. This background is frequency dependent. The background model is composed of a constant component to account for the white noise P_n , the apodization $\eta(\nu)$, and several super-Lorentzian components to account for the granulation and other effects (Hekker and Christensen-Dalsgaard, 2017).

The apodization $\eta(\nu)$ is needed to correct for the finite integration times of the

measurement, and is dependent on the Nyquist frequency:

$$\eta(\nu)^2 = \text{sinc}^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \frac{\nu}{\nu_{\text{Nq}}} \right). \quad (3.11)$$

In summary, the background can be described by

$$P(\nu) = P_n + \eta(\nu)^2 \sum_i \frac{H_i}{1 + (\nu/b_i)^{c_i}}, \quad (3.12)$$

where the super-Lorentzian profiles are characterised by the height H_i , the exponent c_i , which determines the slope, and b_i , which influences the location of the so-called "knee" of the function. The number of Lorentzian profiles used to fit the background varies in the literature, but two to three profiles were found to give good results. The parameter c_i also varies between different methods, and is often either taken to be a free parameter in the fitting process, or set to be four (Mathur et al., 2011). Kallinger et al. (2014) found that, when fitting c_i , the signal is best reproduced by a value close to four for most stars. They also note, that fixing the value to four simplifies the fitting and also gives good results.

The lower panel of Figure 3.3 shows the power density spectrum (PDS), thus, the Fourier transform of the timeseries data of the RGB star KIC 7602732. The individual background components are overlaid in different colours.

3.2.2 Stellar Oscillations

An inspection of the Fourier transform shown in the lower panel of Figure 3.3 shows a clear power excess caused by the oscillations on top of the background. The oscillations cause a series of narrow, Lorentzian shaped peaks in a confined region around ν_{max} . The pattern caused by the peaks can be described mathematically, and gives valuable insights into the structure and parameters of the star, as discussed in Section 3.1.

The interplay of excitation and damping determines the lifetime of the modes. The lifetime directly influences the width of the modes in the Fourier spectrum of a time series: The shorter the lifetime of the mode, the wider the peak. The height of the Lorentzian shape of the peaks is influenced by the intrinsic amplitude of the mode, as well as geometrical effects.

Figure 3.3 shows the full model fitted to the data, consisting of the background model and a Gaussian function $P_g(\nu)$ to account for the power excess of the oscillations:

$$P_g(\nu) = P'_g \exp \left(-\frac{(\nu - \nu_{\text{max}})^2}{2\sigma_{\text{env}}^2} \right), \quad (3.13)$$

where P'_g denotes the height, σ_{env} the width, and ν_{max} the central frequency of the Gaussian envelope of the oscillations. Thus, the full model is given by:

$$P(\nu) = P_n + \eta(\nu)^2 \left(\sum_i \frac{H_i}{1 + (\nu/b_i)^{c_i}} + P_g(\nu) \right). \quad (3.14)$$

3.3 Asteroseismic Scaling Relations

The close relation of the global oscillation parameters ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$ to the parameters of the star, as described in Section 3.1.2 (Equations 3.4 and 3.6), makes them a powerful way to obtain information about the star. Combining those equations and assuming homology between the star under study and a reference star, expressions for the stellar mass M and radius R can be derived:

$$\frac{M}{M_{\text{ref}}} = \left(\frac{\nu_{\max}}{\nu_{\max,\text{ref}}} \right)^3 \left(\frac{\Delta\nu}{\Delta\nu_{\text{ref}}} \right)^{-4} \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff,ref}}} \right)^{3/2} \quad (3.15)$$

$$\frac{R}{R_{\text{ref}}} = \left(\frac{\nu_{\max}}{\nu_{\max,\text{ref}}} \right) \left(\frac{\Delta\nu}{\Delta\nu_{\text{ref}}} \right)^{-2} \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff,ref}}} \right)^{1/2} \quad (3.16)$$

Those relations only depend on the global asteroseismic parameters ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$, and the effective temperature T_{eff} , which has to be measured in an independent way, for example with spectroscopy. The parameters of the reference star are marked with a subscript ref.

In the classical scaling relation the Sun was used as reference star (Kjeldsen and Bedding, 1995), however, over the years several corrections for the scaling relations were proposed. Hekker (2020) summarises different approaches of proposed corrections. Three proposed corrections, which are also used in the further course of this work, are briefly outlined here.

Guggenberger et al. (2016) created a grid of stellar models, and determined $\Delta\nu_{\text{ref}}$ needed to recover the correct stellar parameters of the models. They used the values obtained for $\Delta\nu_{\text{ref}}$ to derive a reference function, dependent on the effective temperature and metallicity. A mass dependence was noticed in the residuals of their reference function for stars with $\nu_{\max} < 170 \mu\text{Hz}$. In a follow-up paper, they developed an iterative process which mitigates this mass dependence of the residuals (Guggenberger et al., 2017). They only considered stars up to the RGB.

Sharma et al. (2016) also chose a model-based approach to the question of how well the scaling relation returns the proper stellar parameters. However, their correction term depends on metallicity, mass, effective temperature and evolutionary state. The evolutionary state distinguished between pre- and post-helium-ignition. Thus, this correction is calibrated for stars on the red giant branch as well as in the red clump.

The reference value for $\Delta\nu$ obtained by Themeßl et al. (2018) is based on the extensive study of three binary systems, each having a RGB star as secondary component. Themeßl et al. (2018) inverted the scaling relations to find the empirical reference value for $\Delta\nu_{\text{ref}}$ needed to restore the stellar parameters found by dynamically analysing the eclipsing binary systems. In this analysis they found a empirical reference value of $\Delta\nu_{\text{ref,emp}} = 130.8 \pm 0.9 \mu\text{Hz}$. Themeßl et al. (2018) noted that the sample size of three RGB stars should be extended to cover a wider range of stellar parameters. Furthermore, stars of different evolutionary states and other properties should be studied to find appropriate reference values for those cases.

4 Data

4.1 Data Collection

In this work, I analysed asteroseismic data. Complementary parameters obtained by other means are very valuable to get a complete picture of the star. In the following, I will describe the asteroseismic data, as well as the catalogues from APOGEE and *Gaia*, from which I obtained effective temperatures and other stellar parameters.

Asteroseismic Data

I obtained the KEPSEISMIC light curves from the Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes (MAST). Mathur, Santos and Garcia optimised the KEPSEISMIC light curves for asteroseismology by using large custom apertures on the Kepler pixel-data files. Afterwards, they processed the light curves with the Kepler Asteroseismic Data Analysis and Calibration Software (KADACS) from García et al. (2011). KADACS first corrects the raw data by removing outliers, drifts and jumps from each quarter. Such artefacts are caused by operational procedures of the spacecraft. In the next step, KADACS combines the individual quarters, while taking into account the variation of the mean flux level between different CCDs.

The KEPSEISMIC light curves were also corrected for gaps less than 20 days using the inpainting technique (García et al., 2014a; Pires et al., 2015). After the described corrections and filling of the gaps, a 20 days high-pass filter was applied. The data are available at MAST¹.

Gaia, Data Release 2

Photometric observations, like the observations from *Gaia* Data Release 2, measure the integrated flux of an object over a defined wavelength range (Gallaway, 2020a). The colour of an object, defined as the ratio of the fluxes measured in two bands, is closely related to the effective temperature. The hotter a star is, the bluer it is. However, the T_{eff} -colour relation is influenced by other parameters of the star, such as surface gravity, opacity, stellar mass and microturbulent velocity, as found by Kučinskas et al. (2005), who calculated synthetic broad-band photometric data for late-type giants, and analysed the parameters influencing the photometric data.

The T_{eff} measurement of the *Gaia* Data Release 2, as described in the paper of Andrae et al. (2018), is based on the distance independent colours $G_{\text{BP}} - G$ and $G - G_{\text{RP}}$, obtained with a low-resolution prism spectrophotometer. All objects were

¹doi:10.17909/t9-mrpw-gc07

assumed to be single stars. It cannot be ruled out that there are binaries, quasars or unresolved galaxies in the sample.

Due to the degeneracy of T_{eff} and extinction, it was assumed that the stars have zero extinction. Andrae et al. (2018) trained a machine learning algorithm using literature values. They combined different catalogues to decrease the effect of an incomplete sampling of the parameter space. However, this procedure does not consider the systematics of the individual catalogues, which might increase the scatter, but decrease the bias of the *Gaia* results.

Further stellar parameters like the reddening, extinction, luminosity, and radius were determined by Andrae et al. (2018) by adding the parallax as input parameter. However, I am only using T_{eff} from this catalogue.

APOGEE-2

Another way of measuring T_{eff} uses the spectrum of the star. A spectrograph disperses the light, such that the amount of radiation at a wavelength can be measured and a full spectrum can be assembled and compared to a model (Gallaway, 2020b).

The Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) includes an infrared stellar spectroscopic survey (Apache Point Observatory Galactic Evolution Experiment, APOGEE), which collects high-resolution, near-infrared spectra. The analysis of the spectroscopic data from data release 17 is described in Holtzman et al. (in preparation). More than 657,000 stars are included in this catalogue. The spectra are used to obtain radial velocities, stellar parameters, and chemical abundances of 26 species. To give an overview of the analysis procedure, I summarise here the analysis of data release 16 as described in Jönsson et al. (2020), which is similar to the analysis of data release 17. For a more detailed description of the changes between data release 16 and 17, see the homepage of the APOGEE survey².

To avoid the discontinuity in the transition between the different stellar atmosphere models, seen in an earlier data release, a new grid of model atmospheric models was computed for data release 16, consisting only of models from the Model Atmospheres in Radiative and Convection Scheme (MARCS) (Gustafsson et al., 2008). The grid was divided into sub-grids, in order to be able to load it in memory.

Jönsson et al. (2020) assembled a large, coarse grid to determine the finer sub-grid appropriate for analysing the spectrum. The parameters obtained by the coarse grid were used as starting values for the fitting process in the fine grid. In the first step, a fit to the entire spectrum was performed, fitting all included parameters simultaneously. The parameters included in this first step were T_{eff} , the surface gravity, metallicity, microturbulence, the ratio of rotational velocity and macroturbulent velocity, and some initial estimates of abundances. In the second step, these stellar parameters were held fixed. Spectral windows sensitive to the element in question, and not sensitive to the other elements, were used to fit the spectrum in this region, and obtain the element abundance.

²www.sdss.org/dr17/irspec/

The greater detail of a better resolved spectrum, makes it possible to extract more parameters than the photometric measurement, leading to more precise measurements. Therefore, stellar parameters from APOGEE are used in this work whenever the star is included in the catalogue. For stars which do not have parameters provided from APOGEE, I use the T_{eff} values from *Gaia*.

4.2 Observational Requirements

In Section 3.2, I mentioned that the length of the observation T as well as gaps in the time series affect the power density spectrum (PDS) of a star. Thus, before going into the details of the data selection, I study and define the criteria for good quality data.

Gaps in the timeseries caused by operational procedures of the spacecraft are common. The filling factor is a measure for the completeness of the timeseries. The filling factor f can be defined as

$$f = \frac{n_{\text{valid}} \Delta t}{T_{\text{total}}}, \quad (4.1)$$

where n_{valid} is the number of valid observations, Δt denotes the cadence, and T_{total} is the total time span of the observations, defined as the difference between ending and starting date of the observation.

To study the effect of the filling factor on the PDS of a star, I chose a RC star with a complete and long timeseries (KIC 2697501, $f = 1.0$, $T = 1470$ days), and reduced the number of valid observations to achieve different filling factors. To ensure that the gaps in the modified timeseries have a realistic distribution, I used the gaps found in the timeseries of other RC stars as template. The stars used as template stars are KIC 8940098 ($f = 0.49$, $T = 1251$ days), KIC 5304582 ($f = 0.62$, $T = 1251$ days), and KIC 9846877 ($f = 0.79$, $T = 1470$ days). Based on the modified timeseries, I calculated the PDS.

Figure 4.1 shows the timeseries and PDS of the test star KIC 2697501 with different filling factors and durations of observation. The oscillations in the PDS are clearly visible for every filling factor. Distinguishing the $l = 0$ and $l = 2$ modes becomes nevertheless increasingly difficult with decreasing filling factor. This can for example be seen in the oscillations at approximately 57 μHz (marked in blue). For the PDS obtained with the higher filling factors (case a and b), the two peaks are clearly separated, whereas this distinction becomes more difficult for case c) and d).

To show that an observation of 1250 days still gives acceptable results when the filling factor is high, Figure 4.2 shows the PDS obtained from the original, complete timeseries, but shorted to 1250 days. Only a small difference is visible between the PDS obtained from the full timeseries and the one obtained from the shorter timeseries. This also shows that the decrease of power in the oscillations in Figure 4.1 c) and d) is due to the combination of a low filling factor and a short timeseries.

Figure 4.1: The figure shows the modified timeseries of KIC 2697501 with different filling factors and durations of observation. The modified timeseries are shown on the panels above the corresponding PDS. The highlighted modes are an example where distinguishing the $l = 0$ and $l = 2$ becomes difficult with decreasing filling factor.

From the above tests, it becomes clear that the duration and filling factor of the observation influences the data quality. Considering the small difference between the two PDS shown in Figure 4.2, I define a threshold of minimum 1200 days as acceptable length for a timeseries. Figure 4.1 shows that a filling factor of 0.79 still gives good results. To not exclude stars which lie just below this value, I use a threshold of 0.78.

Figure 4.2: This comparison of the complete timeseries of KIC 2697501 in panel a) and the same timeseries but shortened to 1250 days in panel b) shows that a timeseries with a large filling factor and a duration of 1250 days does give a clear PDS.

4.3 Sample Selection

LDP Sample

Elsworth et al. (2017) developed a method to determine the evolutionary state of stars, based on the measurement of asteroseismic parameters. This method classifies the stars as RGB, RC and secondary red clump (SC) stars. Asymptotic giant branch stars are not picked up, and are probably wrongly identified as RGB stars.

The mixed modes visible in RGB stars are located close to the nominal p-mode, while for core-He-burning stars the mixed modes are more spread out. Without the need to identify individual modes, Elsworth et al. (2017) used this structure of the $l = 1$ modes to distinguish RGB and core-He-burning stars.

The threshold to distinguish RC and SC stars was set to $\nu_{\max} = 50 \mu\text{Hz}$. They chose this threshold based on theoretical work as well as observations (see Elsworth et al., 2017, and references therein). However, they note that this boundary could be improved by considering the metallicity.

Studying the observed period spacing which can also be obtained by this method, Elsworth, Braun, and Hekker (in preparation) noted a group of stars with period spacings in-between the expected values for RC and RGB stars. The boundary between the RC stars and this collection of stars with lower period spacings was found to be 160 s. In total, 63 stars were found which are classified as RC stars with observed period spacings less than 160 s and observational conditions as defined in

Section 4.2. From now on, these stars are called LDP stars. The ν_{\max} of the LDP stars are in the range 20 to 50 μHz . The selection criteria applied were not optimised for a sample as complete as possible, but instead the criteria were chosen to obtain a sample with the most reliable measurements.

Reference Sample

To investigate the cause of the unexpected period spacing of the LDP stars, I assembled a reference sample consisting of RC and RGB stars. Comparing the distributions of the parameters in both samples gives a first hint towards possible explanations.

ν_{\max} is closely correlated to $\Delta\nu$ (Yu et al., 2018; Hekker et al., 2011a). Therefore, choosing the reference sample based on ν_{\max} also ensures that the stars will have $\Delta\nu$ values comparable to the LDP sample. Thus, I chose ν_{\max} as the parameter on which the selection is based on. I extended the range of ν_{\max} I found for the LDP stars to a ν_{\max} -range of 15 – 60 μHz , which I adopted for RGB stars. The lower limit of 15 μHz was chosen to exclude stars, for which the asymptotic description of the oscillation breaks down. For RC stars the upper limit is set to 50 μHz to exclude SC stars. This threshold is based on the threshold set by Elsworth et al. (2017) to distinguish RC and SC stars. Thus, the ν_{\max} -range where RC stars are chosen from ranges from 15 to 50 μHz .

I obtained the evolutionary state from the APOKASC catalogue (Pinsonneault et al., 2018), which is a combined catalogue of *Kepler* and APOGEE data. Hence, all stars have spectroscopic, as well as asteroseismic data available. The evolutionary state given in the APOKASC catalogue is based on several methods. A consensus for the evolutionary state was formed by applying a selection procedure as described by Elsworth et al. (2019).

From this catalogue, I obtained a list of stars with determined evolutionary stage and measured ν_{\max} . I randomly selected 200 stars, of each evolutionary state, having a ν_{\max} value in the range described above.

The initial number of 200 RC and 200 RGB stars was further reduced by applying the constraints on the observations of those stars as discussed in Section 4.2. After applying those selection criteria the reference sample consists of 115 RC stars and 99 RGB stars. A total of 214 stars is sufficient to make useful comparisons, considering the 63 stars in the LDP sample.

5 Hypotheses

In the following chapter, I introduce possible explanations for the low period spacings we observe in the LDP stars. The scenarios range from events in the evolution of a star like the He-flash, to the interaction between two stars in the form of mass transfer. Other causes like magnetic activity and rotation might also be possible reasons for the peculiar parameters of the LDP stars.

5.1 Stellar Merger and Mass Transfer

Deheuvels et al. (2022) and Rui and Fuller (2021) studied the effect of a stellar merger or mass transfer on $\Delta\nu$ and $\Delta\Pi_1$.

Rui and Fuller (2021) created a grid of single star models with masses ranging from 0.75 to 2.75 M_\odot evolved from the MS to the RGB. With this grid as initial conditions, they modelled a merger event as rapid accretion onto the star. Different merger scenarios were modelled by varying the evolutionary stage when the merger event happened, and the initial and final mass of the merger.

Studying a 1.5 + 1.0 M_\odot merger, they found that ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$ of the merger product closely resemble what is expected for an equal-mass single red-giant star, independent of when the merger happens. However, the evolutionary stage when the merger happens does influence the value of $\Delta\Pi_1$. If the merger happens after the degenerate core as developed, $\Delta\Pi_1$ is hardly affected by the merger event and resembles the period spacing expected for a single star with a stellar mass of 1.5 M_\odot . On the other side, if the primary is still on the MS when the merger event happens, the value of $\Delta\Pi_1$ when the star is on the RGB resembles what is expected for a 2.5 M_\odot RGB star.

Rui and Fuller (2021) explained this behaviour by the physical quantities the parameters are relying on. ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$ are measures of the surface gravity and the mean density of the star. Therefore, stars with almost identical mass and radius are expected to have similar values for these quantities.

In contrast, $\Delta\Pi_1$ is measured from g modes, thus it traces the interior structure of the star. A degenerate core, being insensitive to the envelope, is not affected by a merger event only adding mass to the envelope. In this case, the merger event does not have an impact on the core. Therefore, it does not have an impact on $\Delta\Pi_1$. This results in a value for $\Delta\Pi_1$ which is lower than expected based on the mass of the star. Rui and Fuller (2021) determined that such merger products can be detected based on the mis-match of $\Delta\Pi_1$ and the stellar mass. This mis-match is most pronounced when the mass of the merger product is $\gtrsim 2 M_\odot$.

On the other hand, if the core is not degenerate, it is influenced by the upper layers. In this case, the whole star, including its core and $\Delta\Pi_1$, readjusts after a merger event. Therefore, a merger product is indistinguishable from a single star of the same mass, when the merger happens in the MS phase of stellar evolution, due to this readjustment of the core.

Rui and Fuller (2021) predicted that the identification of a merger which happened after the onset of core-He-burning will be difficult since the values and the evolution of $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RC stars of different masses are similar.

Deheuvels et al. (2022) came to a similar conclusion for a sample of stars lying below the RGB sequence in the $\Delta\nu - \Delta\Pi_1$ diagram. They found that those stars are intermediate-mass stars, and should be located at higher $\Delta\Pi_1$ values, thus, well above the RGB sequence of stars with a degenerate core. Deheuvels et al. (2022) showed that this can be explained by mass transfer between two low-mass stars after the degenerate core was already developed.

Rui and Fuller (2021) did not study how a star which experienced a merger event on the RGB evolves when it starts core-He-burning. It is not clear if the mis-match of the values from asteroseismic observables is still detectable for stars in the RC. The similar values of $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RC stars of different mass likely makes it difficult to detect such stars.

Based on the selection of the LDP stars, I expect them to have similar characteristics as RC stars. However, as Rui and Fuller (2021) described, a merger is not expected to alter the observables on the RC in a noticeable way. Nevertheless, if the LDP stars would have higher masses than the reference sample, it would be an indication of a merger event.

5.2 Mass Loss

Li et al. (2022) reanalysed the catalogue of Yu et al. (2018), and found two groups of stars which are candidates for post-mass-transfer RC stars. Li et al. (2022) measured the global asteroseismic parameters, ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$, and estimated the period spacing. The period spacing was mainly used to verify the evolutionary stage of these stars, and Li et al. (2022) measured it by adjusting the parameters of the period échelle diagram until the $l = 1$ modes formed a zig-zag-pattern.

The first group they identified is a group of seven under-luminous stars. They are found to have radii smaller than expected considering their masses. Li et al. (2022) explained this finding by substantial mass loss during the RGB phase. They calculated evolutionary models with an initial mass of $2.2 M_{\odot}$, and switched on mass loss when the core-He-burning phase starts. Mass loss was switched off when the desired final mass was reached. With a mass loss rate of $2 M_{\odot}/\text{Myr}$, they generated models in the mass range $0.6 M_{\odot}$ to $2.0 M_{\odot}$, with steps of $0.1 M_{\odot}$. Those models show that such stars can recover the asteroseismic parameters which were found for the under-luminous stars.

The stars of the second group they found have stellar masses which would imply

stellar ages older than the age of the universe. Based on the age of the universe, the lowest stellar masses one expects are around 0.8 to 1.0 M_{\odot} , depending on the metallicity. The stellar masses Li et al. (2022) found are as low as 0.5 M_{\odot} . Models with final masses of 0.6 M_{\odot} to 1.4 M_{\odot} were calculated in the same fashion as for the under-luminous stars, but with an initial mass of 1.5 M_{\odot} . For stars with a degenerate core, the structure on the RC is mainly determined by the core mass, instead of the total mass. Thus, the models with initial mass of 1.5 M_{\odot} have very similar asteroseismic parameters. However, the model undergoing mass loss and having a final mass of 0.6 M_{\odot} has an age which is in agreement with the age of the universe.

Li et al. (2022) also compared the radial velocity variations of those stars with a control sample, and found larger variations for the two groups of stars. The estimated fraction of binary interaction is in agreement with the findings of Li et al. (2022). Thus, they concluded that significant mass loss in a binary system happened.

They did not report any peculiarities in the PDS or the period spacing of these stars. As mentioned earlier, it may be difficult to observe the changes of the asteroseismic observables caused by a merger event if the star is in the RC, since the period spacings of RC stars are similar regardless of their mass. However, Li et al. (2022) did not specifically study the asteroseismic effects of mass loss. One can think of scenarios where mass loss may cause a mis-match of $\Delta\Pi_1$ and ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$. Secondary clump stars are known to have higher masses and lower period spacings than RC stars (Bedding et al., 2011). Mass loss of a secondary clump star may result in a star with ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$ similar to a RC star, but with a lower value for $\Delta\Pi_1$ due to the past of the star in the secondary clump. Nonetheless, it is not straight forward to predict the structure changes which would be imposed on a star losing mass on the secondary clump.

Nevertheless, a generally smaller mass found for the stars in the LDP sample may hint towards mass loss.

5.3 Helium Flash

Stars with stellar masses of $M \lesssim 2.0 M_{\odot}$ develop a degenerate He-core after the MS. At the tip of the RGB, they ignite He-core burning in a He-flash, as described in Chapter 2. After removing the degeneracy of the He-core, the star settles into the RC, where it burns He in a more stable manner. 1D stellar evolution models predict that the He-flash occurs in a series of subflashes.

Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018) analysed the impact on stellar oscillations and the expected observable signatures of the He-flash. They calculated the asymptotic mode frequencies of stellar models in the evolutionary state of a He-subflash. Additionally, they considered the height of the modes to study if they can be detected. They find that the oscillation spectrum of a star undergoing He-subflashes will resemble the spectrum of a RC star. Nevertheless, they predict detectable features which could be used to identify those stars.

One effect Bildsten et al. (2012), as well as Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018) mention is the additional evanescent zone splitting the g cavity into two, due to the convective region induced by the He-subflashes. Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018) expect more complicated oscillation spectra during the He-flash, compared to regular RC stars, because of this structure difference. However, the degree of modification of the PDS depends on the coupling between the two g cavities. They expect no strong influence if the coupling is too weak.

Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018) showed how a stretched period échelle diagram changes when a second g cavity is present. If only the outer g cavity and the p cavity are considered, the modes mainly trapped in these cavities will align into a ridge. The modes which are dominated by the innermost g cavity will appear as additional modes around this ridge. The number of additional modes depends on the coupling between the two g cavities.

Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018) expect that ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$ of a star undergoing a He-flash is similar to the parameters of a RC star, since the global properties are similar. The asymptotic period spacing is expected to show differences. They predict that the asymptotic period spacing of the outer g cavity lies in between the parameter space populated by RGB and RC stars. The heights of the g modes in the outer g cavity are predicted to be high enough to be detectable, thus, Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018) predict that this period spacing can be measured. Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018) also described further signatures like a glitch from the H-burning shell and anomalous rotational splittings.

One central question regarding the detection of Red Giants going through the He-flash is the number of stars expected to be in this evolutionary state. Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018) approximated the cumulative time a star spends undergoing subflashes to about 0.3 Myr. This translates to about 35 stars in the *Kepler* sample of 15,000 stars.

Overall, Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018) expect the oscillation spectrum of a star undergoing a He-flash to be similar to the spectrum of a RC star, but with modifications. This might fit the finding that the LDP stars are characterised as RC stars when determining their evolutionary state. The low period spacing would also fit in this picture. Only stars with stellar masses of approximately $\lesssim 2.0 M_{\odot}$ ignite He-core burning in a flash, thus higher mass stars may be evidence against this hypothesis.

5.4 Stellar Rotation

The oscillation modes split into several modes if stellar rotation is present. Thus, this may be an explanation of the more complicated oscillation spectrum we see for LDP stars.

Ouazzani et al. (2013) studied the effect of different rotation rates on mixed dipole modes. They used a model of a star at the bottom of the RGB with stellar mass of $1.3 M_{\odot}$. The core rotation rate was $\Omega_c/2\pi \approx 180 \mu\text{Hz}$, and the envelope of

the star had a rotation rate of 1 μHz . Different rotational profiles were generated by dividing the original profile by constant factors. For this sequence of different rotational profiles they used the code ACOR (Ouazzani et al., 2012) to calculate the oscillation frequencies in a non-perturbative approach.

For slow and moderate core rotation rates ($\Omega_c/2\pi < 20 \mu\text{Hz}$) they found a linear behaviour of the splitting with increasing rotation rate. The trapping of the modes heavily depends on frequency, and determines whether the mixed modes have a more p- or g-dominated nature. For core rotation rates of 8 to 20 μHz , Ouazzani et al. (2013) found that the frequency shift becomes large enough that the nature of the modes differs between members of the same multiplet.

The linearity between the splitting and the rotation rate breaks down for $\Omega_c/2\pi > 20 \mu\text{Hz}$. Ouazzani et al. (2013) notes that this is due to higher order effects as well as the different trapping of the modes. Prograde modes ($m = -1$) are more g-dominated than the $m = 0, +1$ modes. Furthermore, they found that the number of $m = -1$ modes in a given frequency range is higher than the number of $m = 0$ modes, and the number of $m = 0$ modes is higher than that of $m = +1$. The different nature of the modes also gives rise to different period spacings, depending on which modes are considered. $m = -1$ modes have the lowest period spacing, whereas $m = +1$ modes have the highest. Ouazzani et al. (2013) predict that those different period spacings can be identified if the star's rotation rate is high enough.

The study of Ouazzani et al. (2013) is an example of a study considering higher rotational rates. The higher complexity of the PDS may mimic a period spacing as we see it for the LDP stars. Ouazzani et al. (2013) only considered a RGB star in this study, nevertheless, the findings can be a first reference point of the general effects of fast rotation on mixed modes.

In summary, stellar rotation can cause more complicated PDS due to rotational splitting of oscillation modes. It is not expected that the period spacing of rotating stars is vastly different from non-rotating stars, however a smaller period spacing may be an artefact from the rotational splittings, which cause a more complicated structure in the PDS. However, rapidly rotation red giant star are not detected frequently (Tayar et al., 2015). I do not expect the stellar parameters of rotating stars to be vastly different from the parameters of the reference sample, e.g., I do not expect exceptional low masses for rotating stars.

5.5 Magnetic Activity

It is well known that magnetic fields can be present in stars, and can also have an impact on the evolution and the oscillation modes of the star. Thus, I also consider magnetic fields as a possible explanation for the signatures seen in the stars I am studying in this work.

Bugnet et al. (2021) investigated the effect of a magnetic field on the frequencies of mixed modes in red giant stars. One way of strengthening a magnetic field is through a convective dynamo process. This process can enhance a weak initial magnetic field.

Red-giant stars do not have a convective interior, therefore different scenarios are discussed to explain how a magnetic field can be present in such stars. Bugnet et al. (2021) considered a fossil field scenario. In this scenario, the magnetic field results from the relaxation of the magnetic field which was generated and enhanced by the convection present in earlier evolutionary stages of the star. The last convective episode in the life of low-mass stars without a convective core during the MS is the pre-MS phase, where the star is fully convective. For higher mass stars, the magnetic field can also be affected by the convective core, which is generated by the large energy output of the CNO cycle.

Bugnet et al. (2021) used MESA (Paxton et al., 2011) and GYRE (Townsend and Teitler, 2013) to model a typical RGB star to further investigate the frequency splittings caused by rotation and magnetism. The reference star has a stellar mass of $1.5 M_{\odot}$, a metallicity of 0.02, and $\nu_{\max} = 172 \mu\text{Hz}$. The amplitude of the magnetic field was set to 1 MG. The overall shape of the magnetic splittings can be described by a power law in frequency with regular dips in the frequency splittings. The frequencies get shifted to higher values compared to the non-perturbed values. This shift of the frequencies irrespective of their m -value breaks the symmetry of the pattern. Bugnet et al. (2021) assumed that the magnetic field is confined to the radiative region of the star, thus g modes are more affected by it. G modes are also more affected by the rotational splittings, since the rotation in the core is faster than in the envelope.

For $m = -1$ modes, rotation and magnetism play against each other. While the combined rotational splitting from the Coriolis force and the change of the frame shifts the frequency to lower values, the magnetic splitting causes a shift to higher values.

The complexity of the frequency pattern is undoubtedly increased by such effects. As for the rotation, it may be that a lower period spacing of LDP stars is measured as an artefact of the splitting and shifting in frequency of the modes due to the influence of the magnetic field. I do not expect magnetic activity to have a large impact on the amount of metals or α elements in the star.

I also note that a magnetic field in the core is discussed to explain suppressed dipole modes as observed in a sample of red giant stars (Fuller et al., 2015).

6 Analysis Tools

6.1 Tools for the Automated Characterisation of Oscillations

I used the Tools for the Automated Characterisation of Oscillations (TACO, Hekker et al., in preparation) to analyse the light curves obtained from MAST. In the following, I outline the steps to calculate the PDS, detect the significant peaks, and identify the spherical degree of the corresponding modes.

In the first step of the asteroseismic analysis, the light curve is examined for missing data. If a single measurement is missing, the mean of the neighbouring points is calculated to fill the gap.

A high-pass filter of 40 days is applied to the data, before calculating the PDS by means of the Lomb-Scargle periodogram. This method is appropriate for calculating the Fourier transform of unevenly sampled data. The spectrum is normalised by the window function, to mitigate the effect of sidelobes caused by gaps in the timeseries.

The location of the power excess, characterised by ν_{\max} is an important input parameter for the background fitting and the subsequent analysis of the oscillation modes. An estimate of ν_{\max} is obtained by combining three different methods. The first measure of ν_{\max} is estimated from the variance of the time series, the second one is obtained from the mean of the five most significant peaks in the PDS detected by a Mexican hat wavelet transform. The last estimate is computed by using a Morlet wavelet transform to detect the power excess. Those three estimates are combined to obtain a first estimate for ν_{\max} that is then used in the background fitting process.

A Markov Chain Monte Carlo algorithm is used to fit a global model to the PDS of the star. This model consists of a Gaussian fit to the power excess where the oscillations are located, a white noise, and three granulation components (See Equation 3.14). 300 bins are used to decrease the computation time needed for a single star, while still having enough bins to sample the power excess of red-giant stars appropriately. This global fit provides the final ν_{\max} measurement. A background corrected PDS is obtained by dividing the PDS by the background model.

A Mexican hat continuous wavelet transform is used to detect the significant, resolved peaks in the frequency range of $\nu_{\max} \pm 3\sigma_{\text{env}}$, where σ_{env} denotes the width of the Gaussian envelope fitted to the power excess. Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) is used to simultaneously optimise the linewidth, height and frequency of all the detected oscillation modes.

From the list of resolved peaks, the $l = 0, 2, 3$ modes are identified. This is done by cross-correlating the observed frequencies with the asymptotic pattern of the oscil-

lation modes (Tassoul, 1980). The identified radial modes are used to calculate $\Delta\nu$. I visually checked the mode identification for all stars to ensure that the obtained value for $\Delta\nu$ is appropriate for the data.

With the aim of detecting the dipole modes, the spectrum is divided by the MLE fit of the identified even modes. The peak detection and MLE fitting are repeated for the remaining significant peaks, which can either be resolved or unresolved. Following this iterative process, I obtain an optimal fit to all the oscillation modes.

The determination of the period spacing $\Delta\Pi_1$ is an iterative process. Starting from initial guesses for the coupling q , the period spacing, and the offset of g modes ϵ_g , the stretched period τ (see Section 3.1.4) is calculated. The period of the largest peak in the power spectrum of the stretched period $\text{PS}(\tau)$ is subsequently used to update the estimate of $\Delta\Pi_1$. Based on the updated value, τ and $\text{PS}(\tau)$ are recalculated. These steps are repeated until the value of $\Delta\Pi_1$ does not change anymore. All other parameters, except $\Delta\Pi_1$, are not varied during this procedure. In the next step, a similar methodology is used to obtain q , this time while keeping $\Delta\Pi_1$ constant.

Figure 6.1: TACO used $\text{PS}(\tau)$ to obtain $\Delta\Pi_1$. This figure shows the result for the LDP star KIC 6777888. The green dashed line indicates $\Delta\Pi_1$ obtained by TACO. The magenta marker indicates a second peak. However, the $\text{PS}(\tau)$ for this result has lower peaks (grey).

I visually checked the period spacing of all LDP stars where $\text{PS}(\tau)$ was ambiguous. I consider a spectrum to be ambiguous when there is more than one clear peak. An example of such an ambiguous spectrum is the $\text{PS}(\tau)$ of KIC 6777888 shown in Figure 6.1. The asteroseismic parameters of KIC 6777888 are given in Table 6.1. TACO determined $\Delta\Pi_1$ of this star to be 147 s, which is a typical value for LDP stars. The black curve in Figure 6.1 shows $\text{PS}(\tau)$ obtained with $\Delta\Pi_1 = 147$ s. At 147 s, a peak is visible. However, an even higher peak is located at 285 s. The grey curve shows $\text{PS}(\tau)$ obtained with this alternative value. The peaks in $\text{PS}(\tau)$ with $\Delta\Pi_1 = 147$ s are higher than the peaks in $\text{PS}(\tau)$ obtained with $\Delta\Pi_1 = 285$ s.

Table 6.1: Asteroseismic Parameters of KIC 6777888

Parameters	Value
$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	4.068 ± 0.004
ν_{max} [μHz]	32.75 ± 0.19
ϵ_p	0.908 ± 0.004
α	0.016 ± 0.001
q	0.1

Thus, TACO determined $\Delta\Pi_1 = 147$ s to be the value appropriate to describe the regularity in period of this star.

Figure 6.2: Comparison between theoretical and observed frequencies for the two $\Delta\Pi_1$ values suggested from the $\text{PS}(\tau)$ of KIC 6777888. The theoretical frequencies obtained with $\Delta\Pi_1 = 147$ s (top panel) match the observed data better than $\Delta\Pi_1 = 285$ s (bottom panel).

In order to double check such results, I calculated the theoretical frequencies with the period spacings of both peaks in the $\text{PS}(\tau)$. I examined for which value of $\Delta\Pi_1$

the agreement between theoretical and observed frequencies is better. Figure 6.2 shows one radial order of the PDS of KIC 6777888. The $l = 0$ and $l = 2$ modes are indicated in the figure. The blue lines and markers indicate the theoretical mixed dipole modes calculated for the values obtained by TACO. The upper panel shows the theoretical frequencies of modes calculated with $\Delta\Pi_1 = 147$ s, while the lower panel shows the ones calculated with $\Delta\Pi_1 = 285$ s. Comparing these figures shows that the agreement between the observed data and the theoretically calculated frequencies is better for $\Delta\Pi_1 = 147$ s. For $\Delta\Pi_1 = 285$ s, every other mode visible in the observed spectrum is missed. Thus, $\Delta\Pi_1$ is indeed 147 s, and KIC 6777888 is a LDP star.

The period spacing $\Delta\Pi_1$ determined by TACO, as well as the observed period spacing ΔP_{obs} are estimates. The precise uncertainties on a star-to-star basis need further investigation, which is out of the scope of this work. However, the uncertainty is generally estimated to be of the order of a couple of seconds.

I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars, as their $\Delta\Pi_1$ values were found to be far from the values of the LDP stars. Mosser et al. (2014) found that RGB stars with a $\Delta\nu$ of less than $6.5 \mu\text{Hz}$, as included in my reference sample, have a period spacing of $\Delta\Pi_1 < 85$ s. For LDP stars, $\Delta\Pi_1$ ranges from approximately 105 to 160 s.

More details about the TACO code and its computational procedures can be found in Hekker et al. (in preparation).

6.2 Kolmogorov-Smirnov-Test

The analysis of the light curves with the TACO code provides the asteroseismic characteristics of the star. Combined with the parameters measured by other methods and obtained from star catalogues, several comparisons can be made between the reference samples of RC and RGB stars, and the LDP stars.

To measure the statistical significance of those comparisons, I use the Kolmogorov-Smirnov-test (KS-test). Here I will describe the KS-test, before discussing the results of the comparisons in the following chapter.

The KS-test is a statistical test to compare two distributions, and analyse if they are drawn from the same underlying distribution or not. The null hypothesis is that the two distributions are drawn from the same distribution (Sachs and Hedderich, 2006). This test uses the maximal distance of the cumulative distributions of the samples to assess the difference between the distributions.

The p-value is a measure to interpret the result given from the KS-test. Assuming that the null hypothesis is correct, the p-value measures the probability of getting a result at least as extreme as the case at hand. If the p-value is smaller than 0.05, the result is deemed to be statistically significant, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is strong evidence that the two data sets are drawn from

different underlying distributions if $p \leq 0.05$. If the p-value is larger than 0.05, the null hypotheses cannot be rejected (Sachs and Hedderich, 2006).

I perturbed the measurements within the uncertainty, in order to take into account the uncertainty. I assumed a Gaussian probability distribution with the standard deviation given by the uncertainty. On these values, I performed a KS-test. I repeated this procedure 1000 times and calculated the mean of the p-values.

7 Results

7.1 Potential Observational Limitations

Before further analysing the LDP sample, I verified that the peculiar frequency spectra of the LDP stars is not due to features in the data caused by relatively low brightness or high noise level.

Oscillations are easier to observe for stars with higher brightness. To ensure that the LDP stars are not inherently difficult to observe due to a low brightness, I obtained the *Kepler* magnitude of all stars from Brown et al. (2011). In the left panel of Figure 7.1, I compare the *Kepler* magnitudes of the RC, RGB and LDP sample. While the KS-test concludes that the LDP and RGB stars are likely drawn from the same distribution (p-value = 0.09), this conclusion must be rejected for the LDP and RC stars. In Section 7.2.7, I discuss the luminosity of the LDP stars to clarify if this difference is due to the distance or the luminosity of the stars. However, all stars are in the same range of magnitudes, thus, it is not expected that the oscillations in the LDP stars are inherently difficult to observe.

The right panel of Figure 7.1 shows the values of the contamination parameter of the three samples. The contamination describes what ratio of the light collected by the aperture comes from neighbouring stars. Only a few of the RGB stars have high contamination values. The large majority, meaning 94%, 95% and 92% of the LDP, RC and RGB stars, respectively, have contamination values smaller than 0.1. The distributions of the LDP, RC and RGB stars are all likely drawn from the same underlying distribution with a KS-test of 0.38 and 0.11 for the comparison of LDP and RC and RGB stars, respectively.

Considering the similar range of magnitudes and contamination values of the RGB, RC and LDP stars, I concluded that the differences seen in the oscillations cannot be explained by observational issues due to the magnitudes and contamination values of the LDP stars.

In the fitting procedure, a poor background fit can leave too much signal from granulation in the background-corrected PDS, or it can remove oscillation signal. To check that the LDP stars are not subject of such poor background fits, I calculated the noise and the total power of the background-corrected PDS. The range of noise and total power in the PDS is the same for all three samples. Therefore, the peculiarities in the spectrum cannot simply be explained by a high noise level or bad background fit.

Figure 7.1: The distributions of the Kepler magnitude and the contamination is shown for the RGB (blue), RC (orange) and LDP (black) sample. The inset in the plot for the contamination shows the full parameter range. The legend can be found in the left panel.

7.2 Stellar Parameters

After defining the stellar sample and checking the data quality, I now go on to compare the two samples regarding their parameters. The underlying question is if the parameter distributions of the LDP and the reference sample are similar, and what inferences we can draw from them.

7.2.1 Period Spacing

The LDP stars are selected based on the observed period spacing ΔP_{obs} . The asymptotic period spacing $\Delta \Pi_1$, obtained with TACO, confirms the low values for the period spacing, as seen in Figure 7.2 in panels a) and c) where the distributions of ΔP_{obs} and $\Delta \Pi_1$ are shown. Panels b) and d) show the absolute difference between $\Delta \Pi_1$ and ΔP_{obs} as well as the differences scaled by $\Delta \Pi_1$.

Theory predicts that $\Delta \Pi_1$ is larger than ΔP_{obs} (see Section 3.1.4). This is seen for most stars. However, 11 LDP stars have ΔP_{obs} values larger than $\Delta \Pi_1$. From these stars, 8 stars have values differing by less than 5 s, two are differing by approximately 7 s, and for one star ΔP_{obs} is larger than $\Delta \Pi_1$ by more than 12 s. These negative values can be resolved when considering the uncertainties of a couple of seconds in $\Delta \Pi_1$ and ΔP_{obs} , and are not a contradiction to the theory.

Additionally, the differences between the two measurements of the period spacing differs more for RC stars than for LDP stars (Figure 7.2, panels b and d). I will further discuss the cause of this difference in Chapter 8.

Figure 7.2: ΔP_{obs} (a) and $\Delta \Pi_1$ (c) agree that the LDP stars (black) have lower period spacings than the RC stars (orange). However, the difference between these quantities is smaller for the LDP stars (Panels b and d).

7.2.2 ν_{max} and $\Delta\nu$

The global parameters used to characterise the oscillation spectra of a star are ν_{max} and $\Delta\nu$. I show the comparison of these parameters for the RC, RGB, and LDP stars in Figure 7.6. The cumulative distributions in the top left panel of Figure 7.3 and the histograms in the bottom left panel show the ν_{max} values obtained by TACO for the LDP, RC and RGB stars. The distributions of the reference samples are as expected. The RGB stars have ν_{max} values, which are spread out over a wide range, while the RC stars have a peak between 30 and 40 μHz .

The LDP sample peaks around 30 μHz , and is confined to the same region as the RC stars. However, most RC stars have ν_{max} values higher than what is observed for LDP stars. The difference in this distribution is visible in the top left panel of Figure 7.3, where the cumulative distributions of the three samples are shown. The slope of the cumulative distribution of the RGB stars is shallow compared to the slope of the RC and the LDP stars, due to the large spread of values. The slope of the LDP stars is steeply increasing around 30 μHz , while the slope of the RC stars is more shallow.

I performed a KS-test to explore if the differences in the distributions are significant. I took the uncertainties of the values into consideration, as described in Section 6.2. The mean of the p-values computed from several runs is $\ll 0.001$ for the comparison between the LDP and the RC sample, as well as the RGB sam-

ple. Hence, the null hypotheses must be rejected, and one cannot conclude that the samples are drawn from the same underlying distribution.

Figure 7.3: The distribution of ν_{\max} (left) of the LDP sample (black) is shifted to lower values compared to the RC stars (orange). The distributions of $\Delta\nu$ (right) are similar for the LDP and RC stars. The values of the RGB stars (blue) are spread over the complete frequency space for both, ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$.

The distributions of $\Delta\nu$ are shown in the right panel of Figure 7.3. The values for $\Delta\nu$ of the RGB stars are broadly spread out, while the RC stars are confined to a more narrow region. The distribution of the LDP stars more closely resembles the distribution of the RC stars than the RGB stars. This is also confirmed by the KS-test. Comparing the RGB and the LDP sample, the KS-test clearly rejects the null hypotheses with a p-value $\ll 0.001$. For the LDP and the RC stars, the null hypotheses cannot be rejected, since the p-value is 0.068.

Both panels of Figure 7.3 show that the parameters of the LDP stars are more similar to the values of the RC stars than to the RGB stars, which show a different distribution. Since the LDP stars were characterised as RC stars by the method of Elsworth et al. (2017), it is expected that their parameters more closely resemble RC stars than RGB stars, as confirmed by Figure 7.3.

The shift between LDP and RC stars visible in the distribution of ν_{\max} values already hints towards different distributions in mass. Thus, in the next section, I will consider different corrections to the asteroseismic scaling relations and compare the stellar mass estimates of the different samples.

7.2.3 Stellar Mass

In Section 3.3, I described how the asteroseismic scaling relations can be used to obtain the stellar mass. Hereafter, I will call the scaling relation for the stellar mass which uses the Sun as reference star the classical scaling relation. Before applying the scaling relations for the mass to the LDP sample, I investigated the differences caused by the modifications described in 3.3.

Figure 7.4 shows the masses for the RC and RGB stars obtained with the four different scaling relations.

Figure 7.4: The stellar mass distributions derived from different scaling relations are shown for the RGB stars (a), and the RC stars (b). See panel a) for the legend.

For the RGB stars, shown in Figure 7.4, panel a), the correction of Themessl et al. (2018) gives the lowest stellar masses, and the classical relation results in the highest stellar masses. The mean difference between them is $0.28 M_{\odot}$. The corrections of Themessl et al. (2018) and Sharma et al. (2016) agree on a level of $< 1\sigma$. For the other corrections, the stellar masses disagree on a level ranging from 2.5σ to 7.7σ .

For the RC stars, three of the scaling relations give similar stellar masses. On average, the classical scaling relation provides higher estimates than the other corrections, and is in good agreement with the corrections proposed by Sharma et al. (2016) ($\lesssim 1\sigma$), and Guggenberger et al. (2017) ($< 2\sigma$). The correction to the scaling relation obtained by Themessl et al. (2018) gives lower masses than the three other relations, with differences ranging from 2.8σ to 3.8σ . The absolute difference in mass ranges from $0.02 M_{\odot}$ to $0.2 M_{\odot}$.

In conclusion, the scaling relations show differences up to 0.2 and $0.29 M_{\odot}$ for RC and RGB stars, respectively. These differences are caused by the different methods of calibrating the scaling relations. Guggenberger et al. (2017) and Sharma et al. (2016)

used models to study the influence of stellar metallicity on the scaling relations, whereas Themel et al. (2018) used observations from binary benchmark systems to calibrate them.

Only the correction derived by Sharma et al. (2016) is calibrated for both, RC and RGB stars, all other corrections are only tested for RGB stars. This might explain the notable difference of the correction from Themel et al. (2018) with respect to the other scaling relations for the RC stars.

Sharma et al. (2016) noted that a larger correction to the classical scaling relation is needed for RGB compared to RC stars. In Figure 7.4 this can be seen by the smaller difference between the correction from Sharma et al. (2016) and the classical relation in the case of RC stars. Since the scaling relations rely on homology between the star of interest and the reference star, this difference might be caused by the stellar structure of the RGB stars. They are in the evolutionary stage of H-shell burning, whereas RC stars already started He-core burning. Thus, they might have a stellar structure more similar to the reference star, which is the Sun in this case.

Considering the differences in the scaling relations, I applied all of the discussed relations to the LDP sample. This way, the observed trends and results can be interpreted taking into account the differences in the corrections to the scaling relation.

The corrections of Guggenberger et al. (2017) and Sharma et al. (2016) take into account the metallicity. For these corrections the number of LDP stars is reduced, since not all LDP stars have metallicities provided by the APOGEE catalogue. Sharma et al. (2016) found different correction terms for RC and RGB stars. Based on the similarity of LDP and RC stars as seen in the asteroseismic parameters, I applied the correction found for RC stars to the LDP stars.

Figure 7.5 shows the histograms and cumulative distributions of the stellar masses obtained from the four different scaling relation corrections. The absolute numbers of the stellar mass estimates differ, however, a clear separation between the LDP and the reference stars is shown in all cases. For all corrections, the distribution of the LDP stars is shifted to lower masses. The KS-test has p-values of $\ll 0.001$, thus, the null hypotheses, that the distributions were obtained from the same underlying sample, has to be rejected in all cases.

The differences of the average stellar masses of the RGB, RC and LDP sample is in the range of $0.31 M_{\odot}$ to $0.38 M_{\odot}$ when comparing RC and LDP stars, and in the range of $0.33 M_{\odot}$ to $0.56 M_{\odot}$ for RGB and LDP stars. Thus, all corrections for the scaling relation discussed here lead to the same conclusion: The LDP stars have lower masses than the reference stars. This mass difference is of the order of $0.35 M_{\odot}$ and $0.46 M_{\odot}$ for RC and RGB stars, respectively.

This finding can be seen as a direct result of the lower values for ν_{\max} which were found for the LDP stars. However, the absolute values of the stellar masses of the LDP stars should be taken with caution. The lack of understanding of the interior structure of these stars makes it difficult to judge which correction is the most appropriate one for them.

Figure 7.5: The distributions of the stellar mass estimates obtained by four different variations of the asteroseismic scaling relations is shown. The absolute values vary, but for all cases the LDP stars are shifted towards lower stellar masses.

7.2.4 The Relation of ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$

It is well-established that ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$ are linked by a power-law relation (Hekker et al., 2009; Stello et al., 2009). Yu et al. (2018) analysed 16,094 red giant stars and fitted a power-law of the form $\Delta\nu = \alpha(\nu_{\max})^\beta$. They found $\alpha = 0.267 \pm 0.002$, $\beta = 0.764 \pm 0.002$. Figure 7.6 shows $\Delta\nu$ in relation to ν_{\max} , with the power-law found by Yu et al. (2018) denoted by the red line in panel a). The values obtained with TACO are in agreement with this power-law relation.

Figure 7.6: The correlation between ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$ is shown. The power-law relation of the stars (red line, upper panel) and the trend with mass (lower panel) agrees with the literature. A hook feature is visible starting around 30 μHz , mainly populated by RC (orange) and LDP stars (black). The LDP stars in the bottom panel are edged by a black line to increase their visibility. The colour-bar is limited to stellar masses less than $1.6 M_{\odot}$.

Panel b) of Figure 7.6 shows the same data, now with the stellar mass colour-coded. To ensure a proper representation of the masses of the LDP stars, I set the limits of the colour-bar to the mass range 0.6 to $1.6 M_{\odot}$. The stellar mass was obtained using the correction factor derived by Sharma et al. (2016). A mass trend which was pointed out by Hekker et al. (2011a) is visible. For any given value of ν_{\max} , the higher mass stars are located at the bottom of the power-law relation.

In the frequency region of the RC and LDP stars, the distribution differs from the power-law fit. This was already noted by Yu et al. (2018). A hook-like feature is visible, which starts at approximately 30 μHz . This hook has a sharp edge, and can be seen more clearly in Figure 7.7. This figure shows ν_{\max} with respect to $\nu_{\max}^{0.75}/\Delta\nu$. The latter quantity can be derived from the scaling relation for the stellar mass (Equation 3.15):

$$\frac{\nu_{\max}^{0.75}}{\Delta\nu} \propto \left(\frac{M}{M_{\text{ref}}}\right)^{0.25} \left(\frac{T_{\text{eff}}}{T_{\text{eff,ref}}}\right)^{-0.375} \quad (7.1)$$

Figure 7.7: In order to enhance the hook-feature, ν_{\max} is plotted against the luminosity-independent quantity $\nu_{\max}^{0.75}/\Delta\nu$. The markers for the RGB stars have a higher transparency to foreground the hook-feature populated by the RC and LDP stars. The dotted lines are added to guide the eye and mark the edges of the hook-feature.

This quantity depends on the stellar mass M and the effective temperature T_{eff} and is independent of the luminosity (Huber et al., 2011).

Like in Figure 7.6, I colour-coded the stellar mass in the lower panel of Figure 7.7. The dotted line, which marks the edge of the hook-feature, is added in order to guide the eye. This edge is related to the zero-age helium-burning sequence (Yu et al., 2018; Li et al., 2021). I note that the LDP stars are distributed over the complete frequency range of the hook feature, and no increase of the number of LDP stars is observed at the edge of the hook feature.

The stars in the hook-feature are noticeably dominated by LDP stars, as can be seen in panel a) of Figure 7.7. To further investigate if this hook feature is only populated by LDP stars or if it is merely a selection effect, I used the catalogue of Yu et al. (2018) to select the stars which were found to be in this hook. This selection was done by eye, by defining an approximate line separating the hook feature from the bulk of the stars following the power-law relation. The period spacing of these stars was obtained by Yvonne Elsworth (private correspondence).

Figure 7.8 shows the stars which were classified as RC stars with a period spacing

less than 160 s in magenta. RC stars with a higher period spacing are marked in blue. The results from Yu et al. (2018) are also shown in this figure to guide the eye. There is no clear accumulation of stars classified as LDP stars visible in the hook feature. Instead, I find RC stars with typical period spacings, as well as LDP stars. From this, I concluded that the accumulation of LDP stars in Figure 7.7 is merely due to selection effects, caused by the higher number of stars with low masses in the LDP sample compared to the RC sample.

Figure 7.8: Small selection of stars (in colour) located in the hook feature found by Yu et al. (2018). No accumulation of LDP stars in the hook was found. The sample of Yu et al. (2018) is shown in grey.

7.2.5 Collapsed Échelle Diagram

One way to study the regularity in frequency of the modes in the oscillation spectrum is the échelle diagram, where the frequency range of the oscillations is split into segments of $\Delta\nu$ and stacked. A collapsed échelle diagram is calculated by collapsing the diagram in the direction of frequency by calculating the sum of the power of the peaks.

Changing the x-axis of the collapsed échelle diagram to the quantity of $\nu/\Delta\nu \bmod 1$ normalises the values for all stars to the range between 0 and 1. I shifted the $l = 0$ modes to 0.27, in order to align the $l = 0$ modes of all stars. Aligned in such a way, the collapsed échelle diagrams of all stars can be collapsed ones more to obtain an ensemble collapsed échelle diagram. Figure 7.9 shows the ensemble collapsed échelle diagrams for the RC, RGB and LDP stars. In the top panels, the collapsed échelle diagrams of the individual stars are shown. The stars are sorted by increasing ν_{\max} towards the top. The lower panels show the ensemble

collapsed échelle diagrams obtained by collapsing the collapsed échelle diagrams of the individual stars again. I fitted three Lorentzian functions and an offset to the data to be able to compare the height and width of the peaks.

Table 7.1: Fitted Parameters

Spherical Degree/Sample	Height	Center	Width	Offset
RGB				0.09
$l = 2$	0.40	0.13	0.02	
$l = 0$	0.78	0.27	0.01	
$l = 1$	0.47	0.80	0.03	
RC				0.17
$l = 2$	0.35	0.12	0.04	
$l = 0$	0.75	0.27	0.03	
$l = 1$	0.34	0.81	0.10	
lowdP				0.17
$l = 2$	0.25	0.11	0.07	
$l = 0$	0.70	0.27	0.04	
$l = 1$	0.28	0.80	0.12	

Note. – The uncertainties of the fit are likely underestimated. Thus, for a approximate comparison only the fitting parameter are given.

Clear ridges can be seen in the collapsed échelle diagrams of the individual stars. The aligned $l = 0, 1, 2$ modes cause these ridges. The peaks in the ensemble collapsed échelle diagram in the bottom panel correspond to the ridges. All ridges are broader for the RC stars compared to the RGB stars. In RC and RGB stars, the $l = 1$ and $l = 2$ modes are mixed modes. In RC stars the evanescent zone is more narrow which increases the coupling, and thus the influence and visibility of the g modes. Furthermore, mixed modes in RC stars are spread out over a larger range of frequency.

In the ensemble collapsed échelle diagram of the RGB stars, the $l = 3$ modes cause a small hump around 0.45. These modes are also mixed, thus, the power of the few modes which may be visible in RC stars are spread over several modes making the peak broader and less significant. This may explain the lack of a $l = 3$ peak in the RC stars' ensemble collapsed échelle diagram. As an additional note, the offset of the RGB stars is lower than the offset of the RC stars.

In addition, the $l = 0$ modes have a broader peak in the ensemble collapsed échelle diagram for the RC stars compared to the RGB stars. The $l = 0$ modes are radial modes, and do not have a mixed mode character. Thus, the broadening cannot simply be explained by the stronger coupling of the g and p modes in the RC stars.

The comparison of the individual collapsed échelle diagrams of the RC and LDP stars shows that the $l = 2$ and $l = 0$ modes are less separated for the LDP stars. In the ensemble collapsed échelle diagram this is confirmed. The height of the peak of

Figure 7.9: The upper panels show the collapsed échelle diagrams of the individual stars in the RGB, RC and LDP sample. Every horizontal line represents one star. The lower panels show the ensemble collapsed échelle diagrams, where I collapsed the collapsed échelle diagrams of all stars along ν_{\max} . A function consisting of three Lorentzians and an offset was fitted to the data, and is shown in orange.

the $l = 2$ modes is lower than for the RC stars, and the relative power between the $l = 2$ and $l = 0$ peak decreases less than it is the case for the RC stars.

The broadening and decrease of power in the $l = 1$ modes of the LDP stars can be seen in the diagram, and is also confirmed by the Lorentzian fit parameters given in Table 7.1. Another noticeable feature in the ensemble collapsed échelle diagram of the LDP stars is the increased scatter at any point of the diagram.

In conclusion, these diagrams show that there is additional structure in the oscillations in the LDP stars. This is mainly noticeable in the broadening of the $l = 1$ and $l = 2$ modes and the overall scatter, and it is also indicated by the broader width and lower peak height of the $l = 0$ modes.

In this section, I did not discuss the uncertainties of the fitted parameters since they are most likely underestimated. The uncertainties of the fitting routine does not take into account the uncertainties of the alignment of the $l = 0$ modes, nor the uncertainties in $\Delta\nu$.

Huber et al. (2010) made a similar analysis for 800 red-giant stars from the first four months of *Kepler* data. They found a shift in the frequency separation ratios as ν_{\max} decreases. Due to the limited ν_{\max} range of the sample under study, I do not see the trends found by Huber et al. (2010). However, I noticed that the $l = 1$ peak is broader compared to the $l = 0$ and $l = 2$ peaks, as pointed out by Huber et al. (2010). This is a signature of the more complicated underlying structure of the dipole modes due to their mixed nature.

7.2.6 Stellar Metallicity and α Elements

The stellar metallicity $[M/H]$ and its effect on the opacity can have various consequences for the star, and its oscillations. van Saders and Pinsonneault (2012) found that a higher metallicity causes a deeper outer convective zone, Samadi et al. (2010) studied the role of the surface abundance on the driving of the oscillations. They concluded that a lower metallicity causes the driving to be less efficient, due to the lower opacity causing smaller convective velocities to transport the same amount of energy. Karoff et al. (2018) discussed the effect of metallicity on the stellar dynamo, and how a higher metallicity can lead to a higher level of magnetic activity.

The left panel of Figure 7.10 shows the distributions of the metallicity of the LDP and the reference sample. The distributions of the RC and RGB stars are very similar. The KS-test confirms that the difference between these two samples is not significant (p-value = 0.09). Comparing the LDP to the RC and RGB stars gives p-values of 0.00027 and 0.014. Thus, I have to reject the null hypothesis and cannot conclude that the samples are drawn from the same underlying distribution. The distribution of the LDP stars is shifted to lower metallicities, despite the lack of a clear peak.

A subgroup of the elements included in the metallicity are the α elements, which are formed by α particles. These α particles consist of two protons and two neutrons. By adding or subtracting such particles, a sequence of elements is formed which

Figure 7.10: The histograms in the lower panels show the distributions of the stellar metallicity (left), and the α elements (right) for the LDP (black), RC (orange) and RGB (blue) stars. The upper panels show the cumulative distributions. The shaded areas in the upper panels denote the uncertainty of the parameters.

are called α elements, like O, Ne, Mg, S, Si, Ca (Matteucci, 2021). The bulk of α elements is produced in core collapse supernovae, thus, from heavy stars. Iron however, is enriched at a longer timescale, since it is mainly produced by Type Ia supernovae. Thus, most stars with an enhanced abundance of α elements are old stars, which were formed before Type Ia supernovae happened.

However, there is also a group of young, and α -rich stars, which are still under study. A star is considered a young α -rich star if $[\alpha/M] > 0.13$ dex and age < 6 Gyr (Hekker and Johnson, 2019). The stars considered in this thesis are already on the RGB and have stellar masses $< 3.0 M_{\odot}$. The time a star is on the MS is mainly determined by its mass, for example a $1 M_{\odot}$ star spends approximately 10 Gyr on the MS. Lower mass stars spend more time on the MS. Thus, the stars under study are too old to belong to this group of young α -rich stars.

The right panel of Figure 7.10 shows the distributions of $[\alpha/M]$ taken from the APOGEE catalogue. Only 37 LDP stars are included here, since the other stars of the sample are not included in the APOGEE catalogue. The distributions of the RC and RGB stars have a clear peak around 0.03 dex, whereas the LDP stars do not have a clear peak, and are almost equally distributed over the higher and lower $[\alpha/M]$ values. Comparing the LDP with the RC and the RGB sample, the KS-test gives a p-value of < 0.001 for both comparisons. Thus, I could not conclude that the distribution of the LDP sample and the one of the RC and RGB sample are drawn from the same underlying distribution.

Figure 7.11 shows the metallicity against the abundance of α elements. The

Figure 7.11: An increased number of LDP stars is visible in the higher sequence of this plot showing $[\alpha/M]$ against $[M/H]$. In the lower panel the mass is colour-coded, the limits of the colour-coding were set to 0.6 to 1.6 M_{\odot} . The dotted line indicates the boundary between the sequences with higher and lower values of $[\alpha/M]$, approximated by eye.

bimodality which is visible in this figure is well known. It is thought to be connected to the evolution and the chemical enrichment of the thin and the thick disk of the Milky Way (Matteucci, 2021; Khoperskov et al., 2021). Lower mass stars are in general older, thus, it is expected that the sequence of high $[\alpha/M]$ estimates is populated by lower mass stars.

In Figure 7.11, the sequence with a higher abundance of α elements is dominated by LDP stars. I approximated the boundary between the lower and higher sequence by eye (see the dotted line in Figure 7.11) and determined the number of stars in the respective regions. While for LDP stars 19 out of 36 stars (53%) are in the sequence with higher values for $[\alpha/M]$, only 13 out of 115 (11%) RC stars and 26 out of 99 (27%) RGB stars are in this sequence.

This distribution can be explained by the stellar masses of the stars. The LDP sample mainly consists of lower mass stars, whereas the RC sample also includes higher mass stars. Therefore, it is expected that a sequence that is mainly populated by lower mass stars has a higher number of LDP stars. Just like for the hook feature,

the higher number of LDP stars with higher values for $[\alpha/M]$ can be explained by the selection effect due to the low stellar masses of the LDP stars. The result of a different underlying distribution of $[\alpha/M]$ for RC and LDP stars may also be due to this selection effect.

7.2.7 Stellar Luminosity

The comparison of the *Kepler* magnitude in section 4.2 showed that the LDP stars appear to be dimmer than the RC stars. I calculated the luminosities to investigate if this effect is due to a lower luminosity of the LDP stars.

Based on the effective temperature and the asteroseismic radius, obtained from the scaling relations of ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$, the luminosity of the star can be determined. Assuming that a star radiates as a black body and applying the Stefan-Boltzmann-law, the luminosity L is calculated by

$$L = 4\pi R^2 \sigma_{\text{SB}} T_{\text{eff}}^4, \quad (7.2)$$

where σ_{SB} denotes the Stefan-Boltzmann-constant, and R denotes the stellar radius.

Figure 7.12 shows the result of this calculation. I adopted the radius obtained with the correction derived by Sharma et al. (2016). For all distributions, the KS-test gives p-values $\ll 0.001$, thus I cannot conclude that the underlying distribution is the same.

Figure 7.12: The stellar luminosity distributions of the LDP (black), RC (orange) and RGB (blue) stars are shown. The upper panels show the cumulative distributions with the uncertainties indicated by the shaded area.

The distribution of the stellar luminosity of RC stars is confined to a narrow region, as expected from stellar evolution theory. For these stars, the luminosity is determined by the He-burning core, which has a similar size for all stars which start He-burning under degenerate conditions.

The luminosities of the RGB stars are distributed over a wider range, since the RGB spans a range of luminosities.

The LDP stars are also confined to a narrow range of luminosities. However, the cumulative distribution shows that the stellar luminosities in this sample are shifted to lower values compared to the RC stars.

8 Discussion

The LDP stars resemble RC stars based on the overall structure of the asteroseismic PDS, but have period spacings which are lower than expected for a RC star. At first, this was discovered for the observed period spacing (Elsworth, Braun and Hekker, in preparation). For the theoretical period spacing of pure g modes, I obtained the same result. Thus, the lower period spacing was confirmed by two independent measurements.

I found a larger difference between $\Delta\Pi_1$ and ΔP_{obs} for RC stars than for LDP stars. This may be related to a different coupling strength. As discussed in Section 3.1.4, a weak coupling causes the period differences between consecutive modes to vary more around the nominal p modes (i.e., the dips are deeper). Thus, a larger difference between $\Delta\Pi_1$ and ΔP_{obs} is expected if the coupling is weaker. This effect can be seen by comparing the left and right panels of Figure 8.1, where the period spacing between consecutive mixed dipole modes ΔP is shown for a coupling strength of 0.1 (left) and 0.3 (right). The example star is KIC 6777888, which has typical asteroseismic parameters of a LDP star (Table 6.1). I estimated the observed period spacing by taking the average value of the smallest 30% of ΔP . Mixed modes closer to the nominal p mode have a higher influence from the p mode which means that the period spacing between consecutive modes is smaller. It also means that they can be observed more easily, and thus, dominate the value of ΔP_{obs} .

Another parameter influencing the difference between $\Delta\Pi_1$ and ΔP_{obs} is the stellar mass. Montalbán et al. (2013) studied the period spacings of dipole modes in red-giant stars to test convective-core overshooting. Montalbán et al. (2013) found that the difference between the asymptotic period spacing and the theoretical estimate of the observed period spacing increases with increasing mass. The difference for a $0.8 M_{\odot}$ star is approximately 20 s. For a $1.2 M_{\odot}$ star this difference increases to 30 to 40 s. They explained this finding by the dependence of the observed period spacing on the coupling, hence the evanescent zone of the star. The central density, He-core mass and radius of different low-mass stellar models are similar, which means that the density distribution in the envelope has to be very different, considering the different stellar masses. This leads to a different coupling and a mass-dependence of the difference between the asymptotic and observed period spacing. Thus, the smaller differences for LDP stars may also be connected to smaller masses of the stars in this sample.

Nevertheless, it is worth studying how the dips around the nominal p modes behave for different values of $\Delta\Pi_1$. Figure 8.1 shows the diagrams of the theoretical period spacing between consecutive modes ΔP for increasing values of $\Delta\Pi_1$ going from bottom to top.

Figure 8.1: All parameters except for the coupling strength q and the period spacing $\Delta\Pi_1$ are kept constant. I estimated the observed period spacing ΔP_{obs} by the average value of the smallest 30% of the period spacing of consecutive mixed dipole modes ΔP .

The order of magnitude of the differences between ΔP_{obs} and $\Delta\Pi_1$ as predicted from this theoretical consideration and the differences as found in the data, shown in Figure 7.2, agree. In conclusion, the smaller differences for LDP stars are predicted from theory and may be a result of the effects of stellar mass, coupling strength, and the value of $\Delta\Pi_1$.

While the distributions of $\Delta\nu$ of the RC and LDP stars are similar, the ν_{max} distribution of the LDP stars has a peak at lower values. This suggests lower stellar masses.

Although the scaling relations may not be fully understood yet, there is a general understanding of the underlying physical relations leading to them. The scaling relation connecting $\Delta\nu$ with the sound travel time through the star is based on the asymptotic derivation of the oscillation equations (e.g., Tassoul, 1980; Christensen-Dalsgaard, 1988). Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) used relations of the adiabatic sound

speed to the temperature and the pressure of the star to connect this quantity to the mean density of the star.

The scaling relation of ν_{\max} is based on homology of the acoustic cut-off frequency ν_{ac} and ν_{\max} . Belkacem et al. (2011) further investigated the theoretical foundations of this scaling relation. They found that a resonance between the local thermal timescale and the modal frequency is responsible for the value of ν_{\max} . The thermal timescale is also related to ν_{ac} . Thus, ν_{\max} and ν_{ac} are physically connected.

Thus, even if the exact values of the stellar masses may differ for the LDP stars, the stellar mass estimates obtained from the scaling relations are expected to be decent first estimates. This means that the observed trend of LDP stars being less massive than RC stars is valid.

Mass loss seems to be an obvious explanation for the low masses of LDP stars. However, the post-mass-loss candidates discussed by Li et al. (2022) do not show low period spacings. If the mass loss occurred when the star was already on the RGB, the core is not sensitive to the envelope anymore. Thus, it remains questionable if mass loss from the envelope would alter the properties of the stellar core to a degree which would be observable in the period spacing of the g modes. For mass loss occurring while the star is on the main sequence it is likely that the whole star adjusts to the new mass (Rui and Fuller, 2021). In this case, the following evolution would proceed similar to a single star of this new, lower mass. When the star reaches the RC, the period spacing would not be noticeably different from other stars since RC stars of different mass have similar period spacings.

Another possibility is mass loss occurring on the secondary clump, thus, for stars with higher masses which started core-He-burning without a He-flash. These stars are known to have lower period spacings (Bedding et al., 2011). Mass loss from the envelope may have little influence on the core properties. In this case, the period spacing would not be altered, while it would still change ν_{\max} and $\Delta\nu$ to fit the lower mass of the star. However, further investigation is needed to study the influence of mass loss on the core properties and on the oscillation properties in general.

One other possible explanation of the low period spacings is a merger event, as discussed in Section 5. However, it is uncertain if the alteration of the structure caused by a merger on the RGB will still be observable on the RC. RC stars all have similar period spacings, thus, a merger event of a RC star likely would not cause the period spacing to be remarkably different from other RC stars, as discussed by Rui and Fuller (2021). Another clear piece of evidence against the hypotheses of a stellar merger are the low masses of the LDP stars.

Another difference hinting to an explanation are the different widths and heights of the peaks in the ensemble collapsed échelle diagrams. The broader peaks of RC stars compared to RGB stars can be explained by the distribution of the power over more modes due to the higher degree of mode mixing in RC stars. For LDP stars, the peaks are even broader and lower than in the collapsed échelle diagram of the RC stars. Applying the same explanation to them as for the broadening of the peaks of RC stars means that there is more underlying structure in the modes,

which might be caused by splitting of the modes. Splitting of the modes is expected from rotation or magnetic activity in the star. Such a splitting would mainly affect the $l = 1, 2, 3$ modes, while the $l = 0$ modes would be rather unaffected by it. This is in agreement with what I concluded from the ensemble collapsed échelle diagrams.

Other studies of rotating red-giant stars did not report low period spacings (Gaulme et al., 2020). However, the splitting due to rotation and magnetic activity may be able to mimic a lower period spacing. But I cannot confirm nor reject such a scenario based on the analysis of stellar parameters performed in this work. The low masses of the LDP stars remain unexplained in this picture. I also note that a magnetic field in the core is discussed as an explanation for suppressed dipole modes occurring in red giants (e.g., Fuller et al., 2015; Cantiello et al., 2016).

Finally, the edge of the hook feature discussed in Section 7.2.4 is related to the zero-age helium-burning sequence (Li et al., 2021). If all LDP stars would be at this edge, it would be an evidence in favour for the hypotheses of the He-flash. However, the LDP stars are distributed over the complete ν_{\max} range of the hook. The higher number of LDP stars in the hook is merely due to selection effects, since the hook is populated by lower mass stars, as shown in Section 7.2.4.

Stars undergoing the He-flash are expected to have a higher luminosity than RC stars. As evident in the HR diagram (see Figure 2.1), the luminosity increases on the RGB, He-burning is ignited in the He-flash on the tip of the RGB, and then the luminosity decreases again. However, I found that the luminosity distribution of LDP stars is shifted to lower values than the distribution of usual RC stars. This is another hint against the hypothesis of the LDP stars being stars in the He-flash.

Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018) estimated the expected number of stars going through the He-flash in the *Kepler* catalogue to be around 35 stars. The LDP sample consists of 63 stars, which would be of the same order of magnitude as predicted by Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018). However, this sample was not chosen to ensure completeness, but instead we only included the stars with the most reliable ΔP_{obs} measurements. More stars are expected to belong to the LDP sample, which were missed due to the strict requirements posed on the results of the analysis.

9 Conclusion

In this work, I studied stars which were classified as RC stars but have observed period spacings lower than what is expected for RC stars ($\Delta P_{\text{obs}} < 160$ s). I confirmed the low period spacings by a measurement of the theoretical period spacing $\Delta \Pi_1$. The comparison of the parameter distributions of LDP stars and a reference sample consisting of RC and RGB stars confirmed the higher similarity of LDP stars to RC stars than to RGB stars.

The distribution of stellar masses is shifted to lower values for LDP stars compared to the distribution found for RC stars. This explains the higher number of LDP stars in the hook feature of the $\Delta \nu - \nu_{\text{max}}$ correlation, since this feature is mainly populated by lower mass stars. The lower masses may also explain the differences found in the stellar metallicity and α elements. The PDS of LDP stars show more peaks. This higher complexity causes lower and broader peaks in the collapsed ensemble échelle diagram of the LDP stars than in the one from RC or RGB stars.

Based on these results I considered different hypotheses to find an explanation for the peculiar parameters of LDP stars. The outlined hypotheses range from mechanisms like stellar rotation and magnetic activity, to mass transfer between stars, to structural alterations because of the He-flash.

The low masses in the LDP sample rule out the possibility that these stars are stars which gained mass during a merger event. A possible explanation may be mass loss, however further investigation is needed to find out at which evolutionary state the mass loss has to occur to result in this combination of asteroseismic observables. One explanation might be mass loss occurring in secondary clump stars, which can have lower period spacings than RC stars.

The edge of the hook feature seen in the $\Delta \nu - \nu_{\text{max}}$ correlation is related to the zero-age He-burning sequence. Stars which just started to burn helium in their cores are expected to have $\Delta \nu$ and ν_{max} values placing them on this edge. However, the LDP stars are distributed over the complete width of ν_{max} in the hook feature. This is a contra point against the hypothesis of the He-flash as an explanation for the LDP stars. A further argument against the He-flash hypothesis is the stellar luminosity of the LDP stars which is lower than the RC stars' luminosity. The shift to lower masses of the stellar mass distribution of the LDP stars can also not be explained by the He-flash.

The result of low masses can also not be explained by magnetic activity or stellar rotation. These mechanisms may increase the number of modes visible in the PDS due to the splitting of non-radial modes, which may cause a more "messy" look of the oscillations in the PDS. A lower period spacing may be an artefact of the additional modes. However, I note that a magnetic field in the core is also discussed

to cause suppression of dipole modes (e.g., Fuller et al., 2015; Cantiello et al., 2016).

The final answer to the question about the physical cause of the peculiar asteroseismic parameters of the LDP stars is not yet settled. The low masses are a strong indication of mass loss, no other hypothesis provides an explanation for this result. However, further work is needed to investigate possible scenarios of mass loss, the physical mechanisms causing them, and the influence such mass loss events have on the asteroseismic parameters of a star.

10 Outlook

The topic of LDP stars is by no means settled. In this thesis, I studied the stellar parameters of a sample of LDP stars. The comparison with a reference sample provided first insights into the differences between LDP and typical RC and RGB stars. This study can be used as a starting point for further studies using different methods and complementary data.

I found first hints against the hypothesis of the He-flash causing the LDP stars. However, to increase the foundation to reject this explanation, one can search for the observables predicted from Deheuvels and Belkacem (2018). They expect additional modes in the stretched period échelle diagram and glitches created by the He-flash. A detailed study of the LDP stars may be conducted to test these predictions.

Apart from studying the data directly and comparing the stellar parameters of a sample of stars to a reference set, stellar modelling is an important tool in astronomy. Stellar modelling can be used to study different physical conditions and their effect on the structure and oscillations of the star. The influence of stellar rotation and magnetic fields on the oscillation spectrum we observe may be studied with different configurations in stellar models.

Finally, stellar modelling can also be used to study the effect of mass loss on the structure of the star and the observed oscillations. Since mass loss is the only considered hypothesis capable to explain the low masses of the LDP stars, this is the most promising way to find an explanation for the observed parameters of the LDP stars. Studying mass loss occurring in different stellar evolutionary stages can shed light on how the low period spacing combined with the low masses of the LDP stars developed. Modelling the consequences of stellar mass loss in the secondary clump can help understand if this hypothesis is a valid explanation for the observations. Testing the hypothesis of mass loss can also be supported by searching for ejected mass around LDP stars in complementary data.

A Measured and Derived Parameters

The derived asteroseismic parameters, stellar masses and luminosities of the LDP and the reference sample are given in Tables A.1 and A.2, respectively.

I indicate the catalogue from where I obtained the effective temperatures, metallicities and the abundances of the α elements for the individual LDP stars. Whenever a star was included in the APOGEE catalogue, I used the values for this catalogue. All stars from the reference sample are included in the APOGEE catalogue. The evolutionary state of the reference stars were obtained from the APOKASC catalogue (Pinsonneault et al., 2018).

The stellar masses calculated with the classical scaling relation (MClass, Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995)), and the corrections derived by Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18) are given in the tables. The luminosity was obtained using Equation 7.2. I used the radius calculated with the corrected scaling relation derived by Sharma et al. (2016) to obtain the luminosity.

Table A.1: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the LDP Sample

KIC	Cat.	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
2011827	Gaia	29.47 ± 0.2	3.869 ± 0.001	130	$1.07^{+0.03}_{-0.05}$
3121940	APOGEE	27.95 ± 0.19	3.68 ± 0.003	134	1.03 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.02	0.84 ± 0.05	53.3 ± 0.8
3239099	Gaia	31.04 ± 0.29	4.347 ± 0.004	155	$0.79^{+0.05}_{-0.04}$
3945675	Gaia	29.27 ± 0.23	3.998 ± 0.002	144	$0.87^{+0.07}_{-0.03}$
3973137	Gaia	34.72 ± 0.34	3.924 ± 0.006	129	$1.51^{+0.14}_{-0.15}$
4920981	APOGEE	30.99 ± 0.28	4.352 ± 0.005	144	0.75 ± 0.02	0.74 ± 0.02	0.71 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.04	41.1 ± 0.9
5007954	Gaia	29.19 ± 0.22	4.046 ± 0.005	158	$0.86^{+0.05}_{-0.03}$
5009393	APOGEE	31.81 ± 0.24	4.016 ± 0.005	151	1.04 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.05	45.0 ± 0.8
5093559	APOGEE	30.1 ± 0.24	4.091 ± 0.002	157	0.86 ± 0.02	0.83 ± 0.02	0.8 ± 0.02	0.7 ± 0.04	44.6 ± 0.8
5263007	APOGEE	32.7 ± 0.24	4.185 ± 0.003	143	1.0 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.82 ± 0.05	46.9 ± 0.8
5360690	APOGEE	26.9 ± 0.19	3.349 ± 0.002	120	1.27 ± 0.03	1.22 ± 0.03	1.16 ± 0.03	1.03 ± 0.06	60.9 ± 1.0
5445983	APOGEE	29.01 ± 0.23	3.904 ± 0.006	143	0.91 ± 0.02	0.86 ± 0.02	0.83 ± 0.02	0.74 ± 0.04	45.8 ± 0.9
5529403	Gaia	30.58 ± 0.24	4.345 ± 0.004	154	$0.75^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$
5566872	Gaia	29.92 ± 0.29	4.243 ± 0.008	153	$0.78^{+0.03}_{-0.07}$
5781284	Gaia	29.78 ± 0.3	4.088 ± 0.001	138	$0.86^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$
6048066	APOGEE	26.12 ± 0.22	3.617 ± 0.006	154	0.95 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.02	0.77 ± 0.04	60.4 ± 1.2
6278111	Gaia	28.54 ± 0.23	3.801 ± 0.003	156	$1.06^{+0.04}_{-0.06}$
6288543	APOGEE	25.12 ± 0.18	3.562 ± 0.001	137	0.88 ± 0.02	0.84 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.02	0.72 ± 0.04	56.2 ± 1.1
6591089	Gaia	30.38 ± 0.21	4.217 ± 0.003	156	$0.81^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$
6701238	APOGEE	29.1 ± 0.19	4.019 ± 0.005	137	0.84 ± 0.02	0.8 ± 0.02	0.77 ± 0.02	0.68 ± 0.04	44.5 ± 0.7
6777888	APOGEE	32.75 ± 0.19	4.068 ± 0.004	147	1.09 ± 0.02	1.05 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.05	47.1 ± 0.7
6786042	APOGEE	36.76 ± 0.24	4.18 ± 0.005	117	1.47 ± 0.03	1.44 ± 0.03	1.43 ± 0.03	1.19 ± 0.07	66.1 ± 1.0
6922096	APOGEE	29.5 ± 0.32	3.989 ± 0.004	143	0.9 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.03	0.82 ± 0.03	0.73 ± 0.04	46.5 ± 1.1

Note – Cat. denotes the catalogue used to obtain the stellar parameters (T_{eff} , [M/H], [α /M]). The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.1 Continued: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the LDP Sample

KIC	Cat.	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
7018252	APOGEE	27.84 ± 0.17	3.544 ± 0.003	119	1.22 ± 0.02	1.18 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.02	0.99 ± 0.05	69.8 ± 1.0
7049306	APOGEE	34.05 ± 0.21	4.011 ± 0.003	123	1.3 ± 0.02	1.25 ± 0.02	1.21 ± 0.02	1.05 ± 0.06	54.2 ± 0.8
7102567	Gaia	30.8 ± 0.23	4.044 ± 0.002	154	$1.07^{+0.04}_{-0.05}$
7103784	APOGEE	30.78 ± 0.31	4.51 ± 0.006	150	0.64 ± 0.02	0.63 ± 0.02	0.59 ± 0.02	0.52 ± 0.03	34.9 ± 0.8
7188504	APOGEE	30.35 ± 0.21	3.962 ± 0.002	147	0.98 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.02	0.79 ± 0.04	46.2 ± 0.7
7200574	APOGEE	32.69 ± 0.17	3.977 ± 0.005	154	1.21 ± 0.02	1.17 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.02	0.99 ± 0.05	55.5 ± 0.8
7273199	APOGEE	27.64 ± 0.22	4.003 ± 0.003	140	0.74 ± 0.02	0.72 ± 0.02	0.68 ± 0.02	0.6 ± 0.03	43.3 ± 0.8
7612866	APOGEE	30.69 ± 0.37	4.016 ± 0.001	111	0.97 ± 0.04	0.92 ± 0.03	0.89 ± 0.03	0.78 ± 0.05	46.6 ± 1.2
7741385	Gaia	23.28 ± 0.19	3.386 ± 0.003	124	$0.89^{+0.08}_{-0.11}$
7971906	APOGEE	29.94 ± 0.22	4.216 ± 0.005	155	0.8 ± 0.02	0.8 ± 0.02	0.75 ± 0.02	0.65 ± 0.04	49.6 ± 0.9
7971999	APOGEE	30.9 ± 0.17	4.468 ± 0.011	144	0.71 ± 0.01	0.74 ± 0.01	0.67 ± 0.01	0.58 ± 0.03	46.4 ± 0.8
8149325	APOGEE	31.14 ± 0.25	3.919 ± 0.003	134	1.13 ± 0.03	1.08 ± 0.03	1.06 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.05	55.6 ± 1.1
8160099	Gaia	30.68 ± 0.27	4.43 ± 0.003	150	$0.7^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$
8214252	Gaia	28.42 ± 0.25	3.833 ± 0.003	116	$1.02^{+0.04}_{-0.06}$
8277914	APOGEE	26.55 ± 0.22	3.384 ± 0.003	120	1.19 ± 0.03	1.14 ± 0.03	1.1 ± 0.03	0.97 ± 0.06	61.1 ± 1.1
8355654	Gaia	27.31 ± 0.21	3.997 ± 0.001	170	$0.77^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$
8545658	Gaia	30.05 ± 0.2	4.228 ± 0.003	151	$0.8^{+0.04}_{-0.04}$
8682716	Gaia	32.23 ± 0.24	4.066 ± 0.002	137	$1.14^{+0.03}_{-0.05}$
8766273	Gaia	29.88 ± 0.28	4.356 ± 0.003	140	$0.68^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$
9025441	Gaia	34.04 ± 0.27	4.107 ± 0.003	147	$1.29^{+0.05}_{-0.09}$
9076149	APOGEE	29.42 ± 0.29	3.932 ± 0.006	126	0.93 ± 0.03	0.89 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.03	0.76 ± 0.04	47.2 ± 1.0
9334793	APOGEE	27.67 ± 0.2	3.796 ± 0.003	116	0.91 ± 0.02	0.86 ± 0.02	0.83 ± 0.02	0.74 ± 0.04	50.4 ± 0.8
9451434	APOGEE	27.61 ± 0.21	3.567 ± 0.003	139	1.09 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.05	54.2 ± 0.9

Note – Cat. denotes the catalogue used to obtain the stellar parameters (T_{eff} , [M/H], [α /M]). The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.1 Continued: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the LDP Sample

KIC	Cat.	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
9508595	APOGEE	28.31 ± 0.2	4.11 ± 0.004	171	0.75 ± 0.02	0.77 ± 0.02	0.71 ± 0.02	0.61 ± 0.03	51.6 ± 1.0
9514451	Gaia	29.17 ± 0.25	4.252 ± 0.004	148	$0.72^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$
9674113	Gaia	31.05 ± 0.19	4.384 ± 0.003	146	$0.77^{+0.02}_{-0.04}$
9845028	APOGEE	29.65 ± 0.28	4.285 ± 0.004	151	0.74 ± 0.02	0.77 ± 0.02	0.71 ± 0.02	0.6 ± 0.04	51.2 ± 1.2
10063028	APOGEE	30.48 ± 0.2	3.973 ± 0.005	138	0.98 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.9 ± 0.02	0.8 ± 0.04	47.1 ± 0.8
10266793	Gaia	30.27 ± 0.23	4.082 ± 0.004	156	$0.98^{+0.05}_{-0.07}$
10331854	Gaia	29.37 ± 0.23	3.923 ± 0.004	149	$1.04^{+0.03}_{-0.04}$
10527661	Gaia	31.3 ± 0.23	4.478 ± 0.003	150	$0.73^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$
10709704	APOGEE	33.13 ± 0.22	4.114 ± 0.001	116	1.18 ± 0.02	1.17 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.05	64.6 ± 1.3
10723388	APOGEE	31.02 ± 0.23	4.011 ± 0.003	145	1.0 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.05	47.8 ± 0.8
10933244	APOGEE	22.23 ± 0.23	3.287 ± 0.004	127	0.83 ± 0.03	0.78 ± 0.03	0.76 ± 0.02	0.67 ± 0.04	56.6 ± 1.4
10978085	APOGEE	24.58 ± 0.2	3.121 ± 0.004	107	1.43 ± 0.04	1.38 ± 0.03	1.36 ± 0.03	1.16 ± 0.07	97.3 ± 1.9
11080027	Gaia	29.83 ± 0.18	4.247 ± 0.003	155	$0.76^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$
12252899	Gaia	25.6 ± 0.26	3.776 ± 0.005	146	$0.77^{+0.03}_{-0.07}$
12454043	APOGEE	28.0 ± 0.2	3.979 ± 0.004	113	0.81 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.02	0.76 ± 0.02	0.66 ± 0.04	52.7 ± 0.9
12553243	APOGEE	30.66 ± 0.23	4.034 ± 0.006	140	0.98 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.02	0.8 ± 0.04	52.7 ± 1.1
12646386	Gaia	31.15 ± 0.22	4.202 ± 0.003	141	$0.68^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$

Note – Cat. denotes the catalogue used to obtain the stellar parameters (T_{eff} , [M/H], [α /M]). The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.2: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the Reference Sample

KIC	ES	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
1433730	RGB	40.08 ± 0.28	4.077 ± 0.002	...	2.0 ± 0.04	1.74 ± 0.04	1.93 ± 0.04	1.63 ± 0.09	65.5 ± 1.0
1995859	RC	45.85 ± 0.29	4.737 ± 0.002	322	1.77 ± 0.03	1.75 ± 0.03	1.76 ± 0.03	1.44 ± 0.08	67.8 ± 1.0
2424955	RGB	52.05 ± 0.22	5.386 ± 0.002	...	1.43 ± 0.02	1.22 ± 0.02	1.33 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.06	34.5 ± 0.4
2425631	RGB	20.93 ± 0.13	2.567 ± 0.002	...	1.73 ± 0.03	1.49 ± 0.03	1.61 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.08	96.2 ± 1.4
2437507	RGB	20.36 ± 0.16	2.576 ± 0.002	...	1.41 ± 0.03	1.18 ± 0.03	1.26 ± 0.03	1.14 ± 0.06	61.0 ± 1.1
2437692	RC	46.29 ± 0.45	4.745 ± 0.002	299	1.72 ± 0.05	1.69 ± 0.05	1.68 ± 0.05	1.4 ± 0.08	58.1 ± 1.2
2569360	RGB	21.32 ± 0.2	2.722 ± 0.002	...	1.31 ± 0.04	1.09 ± 0.03	1.16 ± 0.03	1.06 ± 0.06	54.5 ± 1.1
2697501	RC	49.97 ± 0.37	4.817 ± 0.002	304	2.06 ± 0.05	2.03 ± 0.05	2.08 ± 0.05	1.68 ± 0.09	66.7 ± 1.1
2832426	RGB	47.56 ± 0.24	4.823 ± 0.003	...	1.73 ± 0.03	1.5 ± 0.02	1.66 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.08	49.1 ± 0.6
3096473	RGB	37.49 ± 0.2	4.265 ± 0.001	...	1.33 ± 0.02	1.11 ± 0.02	1.21 ± 0.02	1.08 ± 0.06	41.6 ± 0.5
3100053	RC	30.35 ± 0.28	3.941 ± 0.002	319	0.99 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.03	0.91 ± 0.03	0.81 ± 0.05	46.8 ± 0.9
3232813	RC	33.06 ± 0.3	4.025 ± 0.001	262	1.21 ± 0.03	1.17 ± 0.03	1.14 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.06	55.9 ± 1.1
3236379	RGB	59.96 ± 0.21	5.835 ± 0.002	...	1.6 ± 0.02	1.38 ± 0.01	1.53 ± 0.02	1.3 ± 0.07	35.0 ± 0.3
3247570	RGB	40.69 ± 0.2	4.244 ± 0.002	...	1.83 ± 0.03	1.55 ± 0.02	1.74 ± 0.03	1.48 ± 0.08	60.8 ± 0.8
3425476	RC	40.07 ± 0.27	4.38 ± 0.002	283	1.54 ± 0.03	1.5 ± 0.03	1.49 ± 0.03	1.25 ± 0.07	60.2 ± 1.0
3527891	RGB	31.45 ± 0.2	3.517 ± 0.002	...	1.69 ± 0.03	1.45 ± 0.03	1.58 ± 0.03	1.37 ± 0.08	64.6 ± 0.9
3553319	RGB	60.42 ± 0.27	5.532 ± 0.002	...	2.12 ± 0.03	1.87 ± 0.03	2.09 ± 0.03	1.72 ± 0.09	52.0 ± 0.7
3660498	RGB	58.55 ± 0.24	6.11 ± 0.001	...	1.21 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.01	1.11 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.05	24.9 ± 0.3
3736289	RC	49.98 ± 0.29	5.008 ± 0.002	308	1.86 ± 0.03	1.84 ± 0.03	1.88 ± 0.03	1.51 ± 0.08	67.5 ± 1.0
3748691	RC	39.2 ± 0.25	4.255 ± 0.002	322	1.6 ± 0.03	1.56 ± 0.03	1.55 ± 0.03	1.3 ± 0.07	62.4 ± 0.9
3834190	RC	33.7 ± 0.23	4.044 ± 0.001	320	1.2 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.02	1.11 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.05	48.5 ± 0.7
3838075	RC	36.44 ± 0.21	4.175 ± 0.002	267	1.37 ± 0.02	1.32 ± 0.02	1.29 ± 0.02	1.11 ± 0.06	54.8 ± 0.7
3936921	RC	27.05 ± 0.21	3.533 ± 0.003	302	1.04 ± 0.02	0.99 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.02	0.84 ± 0.05	49.2 ± 0.8

Note – The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.2 Continued: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the Reference Sample

KIC	ES	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
3946389	RGB	23.92 ± 0.16	2.838 ± 0.001	...	1.66 ± 0.03	1.43 ± 0.03	1.53 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.07	73.7 ± 1.1
3954000	RC	38.63 ± 0.29	4.325 ± 0.002	282	1.47 ± 0.03	1.44 ± 0.03	1.42 ± 0.03	1.2 ± 0.07	61.6 ± 1.1
4039306	RC	33.74 ± 0.19	4.147 ± 0.003	282	1.15 ± 0.02	1.11 ± 0.02	1.09 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.05	53.8 ± 0.7
4065939	RGB	26.96 ± 0.22	3.234 ± 0.002	...	1.34 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.03	1.2 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.06	45.7 ± 0.8
4070891	RGB	43.93 ± 0.23	4.56 ± 0.002	...	1.75 ± 0.03	1.52 ± 0.02	1.69 ± 0.03	1.42 ± 0.08	57.1 ± 0.7
4140726	RGB	50.49 ± 0.35	4.949 ± 0.001	...	1.85 ± 0.04	1.61 ± 0.03	1.78 ± 0.04	1.5 ± 0.08	48.5 ± 0.7
4165109	RGB	20.9 ± 0.19	2.374 ± 0.002	...	2.26 ± 0.06	2.01 ± 0.05	2.14 ± 0.06	1.84 ± 0.11	117.7 ± 2.4
4243803	RGB	16.67 ± 0.2	1.911 ± 0.006	...	2.88 ± 0.11	2.66 ± 0.1	2.9 ± 0.11	2.34 ± 0.15	222.6 ± 6.2
4283517	RC	25.52 ± 0.22	3.347 ± 0.005	242	1.18 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.03	1.1 ± 0.03	0.96 ± 0.06	72.0 ± 1.7
4663478	RGB	43.05 ± 0.29	4.238 ± 0.002	...	2.2 ± 0.05	1.94 ± 0.04	2.18 ± 0.05	1.78 ± 0.1	73.4 ± 1.1
4669400	RGB	44.91 ± 0.19	4.91 ± 0.002	...	1.3 ± 0.02	1.09 ± 0.01	1.2 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.06	34.4 ± 0.4
4672904	RGB	58.7 ± 0.2	6.079 ± 0.003	...	1.3 ± 0.01	1.1 ± 0.01	1.22 ± 0.01	1.06 ± 0.06	29.7 ± 0.3
4760954	RC	45.11 ± 0.27	4.749 ± 0.002	260	1.59 ± 0.03	1.56 ± 0.03	1.55 ± 0.03	1.3 ± 0.07	55.6 ± 0.8
4831888	RGB	53.51 ± 0.2	5.532 ± 0.002	...	1.36 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.01	1.25 ± 0.01	1.1 ± 0.06	30.0 ± 0.3
4939895	RGB	19.67 ± 0.13	2.454 ± 0.002	...	1.63 ± 0.03	1.39 ± 0.03	1.48 ± 0.03	1.32 ± 0.07	83.8 ± 1.2
4946220	RGB	22.65 ± 0.16	2.854 ± 0.003	...	1.34 ± 0.03	1.13 ± 0.03	1.2 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.06	57.6 ± 1.1
4949473	RC	43.84 ± 0.29	4.547 ± 0.002	299	1.68 ± 0.03	1.64 ± 0.03	1.62 ± 0.03	1.36 ± 0.07	55.4 ± 0.8
4991033	RGB	48.91 ± 0.21	5.254 ± 0.003	...	1.28 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.01	1.17 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.05	30.8 ± 0.4
5084662	RC	41.09 ± 0.25	4.485 ± 0.003	331	1.6 ± 0.03	1.58 ± 0.03	1.58 ± 0.03	1.3 ± 0.07	70.1 ± 1.1
5088148	RC	31.65 ± 0.23	3.804 ± 0.002	325	1.3 ± 0.03	1.25 ± 0.03	1.22 ± 0.03	1.05 ± 0.06	59.2 ± 1.0
5091962	RGB	22.38 ± 0.15	2.852 ± 0.002	...	1.38 ± 0.03	1.15 ± 0.02	1.25 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.06	68.1 ± 1.1
5092846	RGB	25.14 ± 0.2	2.914 ± 0.001	...	1.85 ± 0.04	1.58 ± 0.04	1.73 ± 0.04	1.5 ± 0.08	89.4 ± 1.7
5112401	RC	36.89 ± 0.33	4.04 ± 0.001	263	1.66 ± 0.05	1.62 ± 0.04	1.61 ± 0.04	1.35 ± 0.08	70.0 ± 1.4

Note – The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.2 Continued: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the Reference Sample

KIC	ES	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
5112491	RC	45.17 ± 0.27	4.664 ± 0.002	285	1.74 ± 0.03	1.71 ± 0.03	1.71 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.08	62.4 ± 0.9
5112938	RC	45.22 ± 0.29	4.727 ± 0.0	322	1.64 ± 0.03	1.61 ± 0.03	1.61 ± 0.03	1.34 ± 0.07	57.8 ± 0.9
5121605	RC	34.38 ± 0.24	4.088 ± 0.005	324	1.24 ± 0.03	1.2 ± 0.03	1.16 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.06	51.7 ± 0.9
5265256	RGB	52.07 ± 0.21	5.45 ± 0.002	...	1.35 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.01	1.24 ± 0.02	1.09 ± 0.06	31.3 ± 0.3
5517310	RGB	20.06 ± 0.14	2.596 ± 0.005	...	1.48 ± 0.03	1.24 ± 0.03	1.36 ± 0.03	1.2 ± 0.07	86.5 ± 1.6
5525400	RGB	44.05 ± 0.25	4.662 ± 0.002	...	1.58 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.02	1.5 ± 0.03	1.29 ± 0.07	48.3 ± 0.7
5686036	RGB	38.01 ± 0.2	4.269 ± 0.002	...	1.41 ± 0.02	1.18 ± 0.02	1.3 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.06	46.2 ± 0.7
5703348	RC	36.44 ± 0.21	4.263 ± 0.003	306	1.32 ± 0.02	1.28 ± 0.02	1.26 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.06	59.0 ± 0.8
5773063	RGB	48.53 ± 0.22	5.094 ± 0.001	...	1.46 ± 0.02	1.23 ± 0.02	1.36 ± 0.02	1.18 ± 0.06	38.1 ± 0.5
5788354	RC	36.94 ± 0.23	4.282 ± 0.001	283	1.38 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.03	1.33 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.06	64.5 ± 1.0
5940060	RGB	52.57 ± 0.23	5.661 ± 0.002	...	1.19 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01	1.08 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.05	26.8 ± 0.3
6128774	RC	45.27 ± 0.23	4.79 ± 0.003	314	1.64 ± 0.03	1.63 ± 0.03	1.63 ± 0.03	1.33 ± 0.07	65.5 ± 0.9
6140030	RC	39.09 ± 0.25	4.29 ± 0.002	245	1.55 ± 0.03	1.51 ± 0.03	1.49 ± 0.03	1.26 ± 0.07	61.4 ± 0.9
6192431	RC	34.91 ± 0.23	4.098 ± 0.008	323	1.28 ± 0.03	1.24 ± 0.03	1.2 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.06	52.2 ± 0.9
6210900	RGB	43.8 ± 0.28	4.44 ± 0.002	...	1.8 ± 0.03	1.56 ± 0.03	1.7 ± 0.03	1.46 ± 0.08	49.6 ± 0.7
6222355	RC	39.11 ± 0.23	4.375 ± 0.001	261	1.42 ± 0.03	1.38 ± 0.02	1.36 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.06	55.0 ± 0.8
6279068	RGB	47.7 ± 0.2	5.005 ± 0.002	...	1.49 ± 0.02	1.27 ± 0.02	1.4 ± 0.02	1.21 ± 0.06	40.5 ± 0.5
6363109	RGB	55.51 ± 0.25	5.501 ± 0.002	...	1.56 ± 0.02	1.35 ± 0.02	1.47 ± 0.02	1.27 ± 0.07	34.3 ± 0.5
6365867	RC	27.98 ± 0.2	3.67 ± 0.002	327	1.1 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.05	65.4 ± 1.1
6368363	RGB	48.46 ± 0.18	5.312 ± 0.002	...	1.2 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	1.09 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.05	29.5 ± 0.3
6448010	RC	34.85 ± 0.21	4.078 ± 0.002	274	1.33 ± 0.02	1.28 ± 0.02	1.25 ± 0.02	1.08 ± 0.06	56.9 ± 0.8
6504411	RC	28.42 ± 0.22	3.884 ± 0.003	273	0.92 ± 0.02	0.9 ± 0.02	0.87 ± 0.02	0.75 ± 0.04	55.3 ± 1.1
6550823	RGB	46.06 ± 0.2	5.12 ± 0.002	...	1.2 ± 0.02	0.99 ± 0.01	1.09 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.05	31.4 ± 0.4

Note – The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.2 Continued: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the Reference Sample

KIC	ES	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
6591027	RGB	55.0 ± 0.32	5.416 ± 0.001	...	1.63 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.02	1.54 ± 0.03	1.32 ± 0.07	36.9 ± 0.5
6678428	RC	34.88 ± 0.26	4.149 ± 0.005	317	1.26 ± 0.03	1.22 ± 0.03	1.19 ± 0.03	1.02 ± 0.06	55.5 ± 0.9
6681414	RGB	40.11 ± 0.27	4.571 ± 0.003	...	1.25 ± 0.03	1.05 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.02	1.02 ± 0.06	38.4 ± 0.6
6751876	RC	30.28 ± 0.18	3.864 ± 0.004	297	1.13 ± 0.02	1.09 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.05	61.6 ± 0.9
6870779	RGB	53.1 ± 0.2	5.521 ± 0.002	...	1.35 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.01	1.24 ± 0.01	1.09 ± 0.06	30.2 ± 0.3
6951925	RC	43.58 ± 0.34	4.64 ± 0.002	298	1.55 ± 0.04	1.52 ± 0.04	1.5 ± 0.04	1.26 ± 0.07	54.0 ± 0.9
6956481	RC	41.97 ± 0.37	4.173 ± 0.002	306	2.25 ± 0.06	2.22 ± 0.06	2.3 ± 0.06	1.83 ± 0.11	94.3 ± 1.8
6957157	RC	34.91 ± 0.18	3.903 ± 0.003	254	1.63 ± 0.03	1.6 ± 0.03	1.6 ± 0.03	1.33 ± 0.07	75.0 ± 1.0
7100768	RC	25.66 ± 0.2	3.5 ± 0.003	268	0.99 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.02	0.8 ± 0.05	58.4 ± 1.0
7103297	RC	38.64 ± 0.25	4.293 ± 0.004	307	1.48 ± 0.03	1.43 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.03	1.2 ± 0.07	57.5 ± 0.9
7189610	RC	35.57 ± 0.24	4.086 ± 0.006	322	1.44 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.03	1.39 ± 0.03	1.17 ± 0.06	65.3 ± 1.1
7191673	RC	32.11 ± 0.22	3.609 ± 0.001	244	1.63 ± 0.03	1.58 ± 0.03	1.54 ± 0.03	1.32 ± 0.07	69.6 ± 1.1
7205397	RC	28.23 ± 0.33	3.696 ± 0.004	234	1.01 ± 0.04	0.96 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.03	0.82 ± 0.05	48.4 ± 1.2
7270142	RGB	53.64 ± 0.27	5.441 ± 0.002	...	1.46 ± 0.02	1.25 ± 0.02	1.36 ± 0.02	1.19 ± 0.06	32.3 ± 0.4
7346442	RGB	48.63 ± 0.21	5.197 ± 0.002	...	1.37 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.02	1.28 ± 0.02	1.11 ± 0.06	36.6 ± 0.4
7364232	RGB	52.61 ± 0.19	5.619 ± 0.002	...	1.25 ± 0.01	1.04 ± 0.01	1.16 ± 0.01	1.02 ± 0.05	29.9 ± 0.3
7428418	RC	36.13 ± 0.22	4.159 ± 0.003	283	1.39 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.03	1.33 ± 0.02	1.13 ± 0.06	59.7 ± 0.9
7445698	RGB	39.79 ± 0.21	4.129 ± 0.003	...	1.88 ± 0.03	1.63 ± 0.03	1.81 ± 0.03	1.53 ± 0.08	63.2 ± 0.8
7602732	RGB	55.99 ± 0.17	5.952 ± 0.003	...	1.2 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.01	1.09 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.05	26.3 ± 0.3
7672292	RGB	53.51 ± 0.22	5.578 ± 0.002	...	1.31 ± 0.02	1.1 ± 0.01	1.2 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.06	28.4 ± 0.3
7672969	RC	30.02 ± 0.19	3.783 ± 0.004	295	1.13 ± 0.02	1.1 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.05	54.8 ± 0.8
7680159	RC	31.26 ± 0.19	3.673 ± 0.002	247	1.49 ± 0.03	1.44 ± 0.03	1.43 ± 0.03	1.21 ± 0.07	75.7 ± 1.1
7685039	RC	34.9 ± 0.23	4.205 ± 0.001	299	1.26 ± 0.03	1.23 ± 0.03	1.21 ± 0.03	1.02 ± 0.06	63.2 ± 1.1

Note – The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.2 Continued: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the Reference Sample

KIC	ES	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
7743539	RC	41.21 ± 0.24	4.461 ± 0.002	291	1.58 ± 0.03	1.55 ± 0.03	1.54 ± 0.03	1.29 ± 0.07	62.4 ± 0.9
7802549	RC	31.6 ± 0.22	3.997 ± 0.002	291	1.09 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.02	0.88 ± 0.05	52.2 ± 0.8
7834159	RC	39.13 ± 0.27	4.407 ± 0.003	291	1.43 ± 0.03	1.4 ± 0.03	1.38 ± 0.03	1.16 ± 0.06	60.2 ± 1.0
7944038	RGB	19.9 ± 0.17	2.331 ± 0.004	...	2.19 ± 0.06	1.93 ± 0.05	2.1 ± 0.05	1.78 ± 0.1	131.4 ± 2.5
7956671	RGB	42.86 ± 0.28	4.413 ± 0.002	...	1.78 ± 0.04	1.54 ± 0.03	1.7 ± 0.03	1.45 ± 0.08	54.2 ± 0.8
7967534	RC	30.3 ± 0.22	4.257 ± 0.003	264	0.72 ± 0.02	0.71 ± 0.02	0.65 ± 0.01	0.59 ± 0.03	34.7 ± 0.6
7970207	RGB	49.91 ± 0.17	5.385 ± 0.003	...	1.24 ± 0.01	1.03 ± 0.01	1.13 ± 0.01	1.01 ± 0.05	29.8 ± 0.3
8078554	RC	35.63 ± 0.19	4.202 ± 0.003	317	1.3 ± 0.02	1.26 ± 0.02	1.24 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.06	59.0 ± 0.8
8082494	RC	31.99 ± 0.25	3.824 ± 0.003	315	1.31 ± 0.03	1.26 ± 0.03	1.22 ± 0.03	1.06 ± 0.06	58.5 ± 1.0
8160419	RGB	23.95 ± 0.16	2.96 ± 0.001	...	1.38 ± 0.03	1.16 ± 0.02	1.24 ± 0.02	1.12 ± 0.06	57.0 ± 0.8
8160637	RGB	54.65 ± 0.2	5.508 ± 0.002	...	1.48 ± 0.02	1.27 ± 0.01	1.38 ± 0.02	1.2 ± 0.06	32.6 ± 0.3
8165444	RC	41.04 ± 0.24	4.483 ± 0.002	331	1.54 ± 0.03	1.51 ± 0.03	1.5 ± 0.03	1.25 ± 0.07	61.7 ± 0.9
8173148	RC	34.7 ± 0.22	4.136 ± 0.002	277	1.24 ± 0.02	1.19 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.05	52.6 ± 0.8
8213138	RGB	59.57 ± 0.21	6.134 ± 0.002	...	1.25 ± 0.01	1.05 ± 0.01	1.15 ± 0.01	1.01 ± 0.05	24.8 ± 0.2
8223927	RGB	53.44 ± 0.17	5.641 ± 0.002	...	1.26 ± 0.01	1.05 ± 0.01	1.15 ± 0.01	1.03 ± 0.05	27.9 ± 0.3
8233917	RC	30.03 ± 0.21	3.79 ± 0.003	278	1.1 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.05	49.0 ± 0.8
8241402	RC	29.72 ± 0.21	3.772 ± 0.002	277	1.09 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.05	50.4 ± 0.9
8350645	RGB	54.25 ± 0.23	5.242 ± 0.001	...	1.79 ± 0.02	1.56 ± 0.02	1.71 ± 0.02	1.46 ± 0.08	42.0 ± 0.4
8364578	RC	28.54 ± 0.2	3.671 ± 0.005	332	1.17 ± 0.03	1.13 ± 0.02	1.1 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.05	68.9 ± 1.3
8386921	RC	26.79 ± 0.21	3.451 ± 0.002	317	1.14 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.05	58.1 ± 1.0
8489832	RC	40.35 ± 0.28	4.459 ± 0.004	279	1.46 ± 0.03	1.43 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.03	1.19 ± 0.07	56.7 ± 0.9
8612393	RGB	48.0 ± 0.18	5.274 ± 0.001	...	1.21 ± 0.01	1.0 ± 0.01	1.1 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.05	30.5 ± 0.4
8617244	RGB	30.22 ± 0.26	3.549 ± 0.002	...	1.51 ± 0.04	1.27 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.04	1.23 ± 0.07	65.1 ± 1.3

Note – The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.2 Continued: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the Reference Sample

KIC	ES	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
8623850	RGB	53.74 ± 0.17	5.796 ± 0.003	...	1.17 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01	1.07 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.05	26.5 ± 0.3
8686389	RC	23.83 ± 0.21	2.962 ± 0.002	218	1.43 ± 0.04	1.37 ± 0.04	1.32 ± 0.03	1.16 ± 0.07	76.3 ± 1.4
8737047	RGB	23.34 ± 0.18	2.947 ± 0.002	...	1.34 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.03	1.21 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.06	60.2 ± 1.1
8803432	RC	31.91 ± 0.2	3.998 ± 0.003	281	1.13 ± 0.02	1.08 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.05	55.5 ± 0.8
8815290	RGB	44.98 ± 0.32	4.417 ± 0.003	...	2.12 ± 0.05	1.86 ± 0.04	2.09 ± 0.05	1.72 ± 0.1	67.3 ± 1.1
8826496	RC	43.47 ± 0.3	4.677 ± 0.002	278	1.57 ± 0.03	1.55 ± 0.03	1.55 ± 0.03	1.28 ± 0.07	62.3 ± 1.0
8866716	RGB	37.84 ± 0.23	4.339 ± 0.002	...	1.28 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.02	1.17 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.06	40.1 ± 0.7
8937073	RC	25.06 ± 0.23	3.231 ± 0.002	208	1.22 ± 0.03	1.16 ± 0.03	1.13 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.06	67.4 ± 1.3
8939889	RC	35.22 ± 0.23	4.028 ± 0.0	316	1.4 ± 0.03	1.36 ± 0.03	1.32 ± 0.03	1.14 ± 0.06	55.9 ± 0.9
9008090	RC	37.1 ± 0.24	4.292 ± 0.002	311	1.32 ± 0.03	1.28 ± 0.03	1.25 ± 0.03	1.07 ± 0.06	54.8 ± 0.9
9009805	RGB	50.42 ± 0.19	5.163 ± 0.001	...	1.6 ± 0.02	1.38 ± 0.02	1.53 ± 0.02	1.3 ± 0.07	44.5 ± 0.5
9020419	RC	33.37 ± 0.19	4.145 ± 0.003	333	1.18 ± 0.02	1.17 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.05	64.6 ± 0.9
9028880	RGB	43.36 ± 0.2	4.783 ± 0.002	...	1.27 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.02	1.03 ± 0.05	32.9 ± 0.4
9077844	RC	47.23 ± 0.28	4.699 ± 0.002	244	1.83 ± 0.03	1.8 ± 0.03	1.78 ± 0.03	1.49 ± 0.08	55.4 ± 0.7
9145952	RC	33.48 ± 0.2	4.07 ± 0.003	264	1.2 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.02	1.13 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.05	55.2 ± 0.8
9268349	RGB	58.68 ± 0.18	6.2 ± 0.002	...	1.18 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01	1.09 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.05	25.6 ± 0.3
9269772	RGB	58.89 ± 0.22	5.892 ± 0.002	...	1.42 ± 0.02	1.21 ± 0.01	1.32 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.06	29.2 ± 0.3
9282363	RC	29.47 ± 0.21	3.741 ± 0.002	316	1.12 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.05	55.2 ± 0.9
9332840	RC	39.97 ± 0.24	4.429 ± 0.002	300	1.43 ± 0.03	1.39 ± 0.03	1.36 ± 0.03	1.16 ± 0.06	52.4 ± 0.8
9333501	RGB	27.13 ± 0.17	3.471 ± 0.002	...	1.16 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.05	49.9 ± 0.7
9336090	RC	32.75 ± 0.19	4.042 ± 0.003	260	1.19 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.02	1.12 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.05	58.9 ± 0.8
9450786	RC	27.97 ± 0.22	3.619 ± 0.002	269	1.15 ± 0.03	1.11 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.05	67.4 ± 1.2
9469212	RC	42.92 ± 0.55	4.389 ± 0.002	232	1.8 ± 0.07	1.76 ± 0.07	1.74 ± 0.07	1.47 ± 0.09	59.8 ± 1.7

Note – The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.2 Continued: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the Reference Sample

KIC	ES	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
9532518	RC	31.44 ± 0.21	3.972 ± 0.002	289	1.12 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.02	1.05 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.05	56.6 ± 0.9
9635490	RGB	15.06 ± 0.13	2.139 ± 0.005	...	1.25 ± 0.04	1.04 ± 0.03	1.11 ± 0.03	1.01 ± 0.06	79.0 ± 1.7
9650881	RC	36.11 ± 0.2	4.067 ± 0.003	242	1.46 ± 0.02	1.41 ± 0.02	1.37 ± 0.02	1.18 ± 0.06	56.8 ± 0.8
9702609	RGB	45.87 ± 0.22	4.937 ± 0.003	...	1.38 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.02	1.27 ± 0.02	1.12 ± 0.06	36.9 ± 0.5
9713083	RC	41.3 ± 0.26	4.533 ± 0.002	304	1.47 ± 0.03	1.44 ± 0.03	1.42 ± 0.03	1.2 ± 0.07	55.9 ± 0.8
9716994	RC	31.53 ± 0.24	4.106 ± 0.005	324	0.99 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.8 ± 0.05	50.6 ± 0.9
9718024	RC	34.29 ± 0.19	4.136 ± 0.003	336	1.28 ± 0.02	1.26 ± 0.02	1.23 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.06	66.0 ± 1.0
9766906	RC	25.68 ± 0.23	3.419 ± 0.003	244	1.04 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.03	0.84 ± 0.05	55.0 ± 1.1
9773214	RGB	43.36 ± 0.19	4.959 ± 0.002	...	1.18 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.01	1.08 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.05	35.1 ± 0.4
9779963	RGB	33.03 ± 0.23	3.553 ± 0.002	...	1.93 ± 0.04	1.67 ± 0.04	1.84 ± 0.04	1.57 ± 0.09	74.9 ± 1.3
9784946	RGB	57.54 ± 0.23	5.693 ± 0.002	...	1.53 ± 0.02	1.32 ± 0.02	1.44 ± 0.02	1.24 ± 0.07	33.0 ± 0.3
9815488	RC	36.56 ± 0.23	4.297 ± 0.004	317	1.29 ± 0.03	1.26 ± 0.02	1.24 ± 0.02	1.05 ± 0.06	58.1 ± 0.9
9827682	RGB	37.01 ± 0.2	4.119 ± 0.003	...	1.45 ± 0.02	1.23 ± 0.02	1.33 ± 0.02	1.17 ± 0.06	45.2 ± 0.7
9843754	RC	30.17 ± 0.3	3.759 ± 0.001	319	1.14 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.05	49.5 ± 1.1
9846355	RC	32.04 ± 0.19	3.859 ± 0.003	259	1.23 ± 0.02	1.19 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.05	51.6 ± 0.7
9846877	RC	36.83 ± 0.23	4.267 ± 0.003	259	1.32 ± 0.03	1.28 ± 0.02	1.26 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.06	55.2 ± 0.8
9882550	RC	37.13 ± 0.2	4.238 ± 0.004	246	1.42 ± 0.02	1.37 ± 0.02	1.36 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.06	60.8 ± 0.9
9899323	RC	36.14 ± 0.22	4.237 ± 0.006	298	1.32 ± 0.03	1.28 ± 0.02	1.26 ± 0.02	1.07 ± 0.06	59.3 ± 1.0
9941713	RGB	48.42 ± 0.28	4.833 ± 0.002	...	1.78 ± 0.03	1.54 ± 0.03	1.7 ± 0.03	1.44 ± 0.08	47.2 ± 0.6
9962729	RGB	52.0 ± 0.21	5.407 ± 0.003	...	1.34 ± 0.02	1.13 ± 0.01	1.22 ± 0.02	1.09 ± 0.06	28.9 ± 0.3
9995162	RGB	55.45 ± 0.25	5.632 ± 0.002	...	1.41 ± 0.02	1.2 ± 0.02	1.31 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.06	30.2 ± 0.3
10003419	RC	35.98 ± 0.21	4.117 ± 0.005	243	1.39 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.02	1.31 ± 0.02	1.13 ± 0.06	56.3 ± 0.8
10018239	RC	31.78 ± 0.26	4.029 ± 0.004	291	1.0 ± 0.03	0.96 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.05	41.1 ± 0.7

Note – The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.2 Continued: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the Reference Sample

KIC	ES	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
10024460	RGB	35.91 ± 0.15	4.113 ± 0.002	...	1.3 ± 0.02	1.09 ± 0.01	1.17 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.06	39.1 ± 0.5
10095409	RGB	39.89 ± 0.25	4.152 ± 0.001	...	1.84 ± 0.03	1.59 ± 0.03	1.77 ± 0.03	1.5 ± 0.08	60.8 ± 0.9
10154247	RC	31.25 ± 0.25	3.878 ± 0.001	210	1.18 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.05	55.7 ± 1.2
10161943	RGB	60.35 ± 0.17	6.252 ± 0.003	...	1.21 ± 0.01	1.01 ± 0.01	1.11 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.05	24.1 ± 0.2
10200886	RGB	37.69 ± 0.23	4.173 ± 0.002	...	1.55 ± 0.03	1.32 ± 0.02	1.46 ± 0.03	1.26 ± 0.07	55.3 ± 0.9
10203168	RC	30.47 ± 0.29	3.979 ± 0.002	289	1.01 ± 0.03	0.98 ± 0.03	0.95 ± 0.03	0.82 ± 0.05	53.4 ± 1.1
10220865	RC	30.81 ± 0.27	3.957 ± 0.005	337	1.08 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.03	1.01 ± 0.03	0.87 ± 0.05	57.2 ± 1.3
10268744	RC	32.83 ± 0.19	3.746 ± 0.003	215	1.47 ± 0.03	1.41 ± 0.03	1.36 ± 0.02	1.19 ± 0.06	57.4 ± 0.8
10320170	RGB	24.63 ± 0.19	2.922 ± 0.001	...	1.63 ± 0.04	1.4 ± 0.03	1.5 ± 0.03	1.33 ± 0.07	71.7 ± 1.2
10328498	RGB	43.05 ± 0.28	4.544 ± 0.002	...	1.61 ± 0.03	1.39 ± 0.03	1.53 ± 0.03	1.31 ± 0.07	49.0 ± 0.7
10459794	RGB	46.11 ± 0.29	4.771 ± 0.002	...	1.61 ± 0.03	1.38 ± 0.03	1.51 ± 0.03	1.31 ± 0.07	43.9 ± 0.6
10548201	RGB	59.08 ± 0.29	5.856 ± 0.003	...	1.59 ± 0.02	1.39 ± 0.02	1.54 ± 0.02	1.29 ± 0.07	40.2 ± 0.5
10602374	RC	38.3 ± 0.23	4.208 ± 0.003	326	1.53 ± 0.03	1.49 ± 0.03	1.45 ± 0.03	1.24 ± 0.07	57.7 ± 0.8
10604255	RC	30.19 ± 0.22	3.911 ± 0.006	281	1.0 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.02	0.91 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.05	45.7 ± 0.8
10614707	RC	35.07 ± 0.25	4.261 ± 0.008	288	1.18 ± 0.03	1.15 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.03	0.96 ± 0.05	55.2 ± 1.0
10664514	RC	31.07 ± 0.24	4.133 ± 0.002	294	0.95 ± 0.02	0.93 ± 0.02	0.9 ± 0.02	0.77 ± 0.04	53.7 ± 1.0
10749954	RC	32.89 ± 0.26	4.075 ± 0.003	326	1.19 ± 0.03	1.17 ± 0.03	1.15 ± 0.03	0.97 ± 0.05	63.4 ± 1.2
10799530	RC	37.27 ± 0.25	4.233 ± 0.002	292	1.39 ± 0.03	1.34 ± 0.03	1.31 ± 0.03	1.13 ± 0.06	54.5 ± 0.8
10817647	RGB	48.62 ± 0.25	5.129 ± 0.002	...	1.45 ± 0.02	1.24 ± 0.02	1.37 ± 0.02	1.18 ± 0.06	39.9 ± 0.5
10853817	RGB	60.66 ± 0.22	6.187 ± 0.002	...	1.33 ± 0.01	1.13 ± 0.01	1.24 ± 0.01	1.08 ± 0.06	28.9 ± 0.3
10857579	RGB	31.46 ± 0.14	3.853 ± 0.003	...	1.2 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.01	1.08 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.05	44.9 ± 0.7
10864711	RGB	45.04 ± 0.21	4.849 ± 0.002	...	1.39 ± 0.02	1.18 ± 0.02	1.29 ± 0.02	1.13 ± 0.06	37.6 ± 0.4
10931902	RC	33.91 ± 0.25	3.959 ± 0.001	234	1.31 ± 0.03	1.26 ± 0.03	1.21 ± 0.03	1.06 ± 0.06	50.9 ± 0.9

Note – The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

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KIC	ES	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
10989954	RGB	57.56 ± 0.21	5.791 ± 0.002	...	1.43 ± 0.02	1.22 ± 0.01	1.33 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.06	30.4 ± 0.3
10990704	RC	29.54 ± 0.27	3.946 ± 0.002	325	0.94 ± 0.03	0.89 ± 0.02	0.86 ± 0.02	0.76 ± 0.04	48.3 ± 1.0
10992345	RGB	56.85 ± 0.22	5.832 ± 0.002	...	1.33 ± 0.02	1.13 ± 0.01	1.24 ± 0.01	1.08 ± 0.06	28.4 ± 0.3
11028575	RC	36.47 ± 0.27	4.246 ± 0.003	335	1.34 ± 0.03	1.3 ± 0.03	1.28 ± 0.03	1.09 ± 0.06	59.2 ± 1.0
11031856	RC	27.27 ± 0.24	3.607 ± 0.001	315	1.09 ± 0.03	1.06 ± 0.03	1.03 ± 0.03	0.89 ± 0.05	66.8 ± 1.3
11043820	RGB	47.76 ± 0.23	5.284 ± 0.001	...	1.17 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.01	1.06 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.05	28.8 ± 0.4
11083701	RC	31.52 ± 0.2	3.843 ± 0.003	229	1.23 ± 0.02	1.17 ± 0.02	1.14 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.05	55.4 ± 0.8
11084022	RGB	44.89 ± 0.2	4.645 ± 0.002	...	1.64 ± 0.02	1.41 ± 0.02	1.55 ± 0.02	1.34 ± 0.07	45.7 ± 0.5
11087963	RC	44.28 ± 0.26	4.669 ± 0.003	313	1.6 ± 0.03	1.56 ± 0.03	1.55 ± 0.03	1.3 ± 0.07	55.8 ± 0.8
11090395	RC	37.1 ± 0.23	4.274 ± 0.002	258	1.38 ± 0.03	1.35 ± 0.03	1.33 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.06	62.0 ± 0.9
11099193	RGB	53.97 ± 0.25	5.548 ± 0.002	...	1.39 ± 0.02	1.19 ± 0.02	1.29 ± 0.02	1.13 ± 0.06	31.3 ± 0.4
11153026	RC	37.38 ± 0.24	4.363 ± 0.003	306	1.33 ± 0.03	1.31 ± 0.03	1.29 ± 0.03	1.08 ± 0.06	62.3 ± 0.9
11190322	RGB	54.93 ± 0.2	5.482 ± 0.002	...	1.51 ± 0.02	1.3 ± 0.01	1.41 ± 0.02	1.23 ± 0.06	32.4 ± 0.3
11251096	RGB	25.91 ± 0.23	3.274 ± 0.003	...	1.28 ± 0.03	1.06 ± 0.03	1.17 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.06	60.0 ± 1.3
11299667	RGB	46.9 ± 0.24	5.125 ± 0.002	...	1.27 ± 0.02	1.05 ± 0.02	1.16 ± 0.02	1.03 ± 0.05	32.7 ± 0.4
11358810	RC	36.32 ± 0.21	4.346 ± 0.003	319	1.28 ± 0.02	1.28 ± 0.02	1.26 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.06	68.0 ± 1.1
11395438	RC	33.78 ± 0.23	4.134 ± 0.003	311	1.15 ± 0.02	1.11 ± 0.02	1.08 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.05	51.8 ± 0.8
11508336	RC	30.31 ± 0.25	3.8 ± 0.003	267	1.25 ± 0.03	1.22 ± 0.03	1.19 ± 0.03	1.01 ± 0.06	73.9 ± 1.4
11566273	RGB	58.38 ± 0.22	5.819 ± 0.002	...	1.47 ± 0.02	1.26 ± 0.02	1.38 ± 0.02	1.19 ± 0.06	31.4 ± 0.5
11569659	RC	31.75 ± 0.2	4.049 ± 0.002	291	1.08 ± 0.02	1.04 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.02	0.87 ± 0.05	55.8 ± 0.8
11615224	RC	30.32 ± 0.22	4.051 ± 0.002	257	0.89 ± 0.02	0.86 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.02	0.72 ± 0.04	42.4 ± 0.7
11670968	RGB	45.35 ± 0.21	5.046 ± 0.002	...	1.23 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.01	1.12 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.05	33.4 ± 0.4
11774110	RC	35.14 ± 0.25	4.036 ± 0.005	245	1.38 ± 0.03	1.34 ± 0.03	1.3 ± 0.03	1.12 ± 0.06	55.4 ± 0.9

Note – The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

Table A.2 Continued: Asteroseismic Parameters and Stellar Masses of the Reference Sample

KIC	ES	ν_{\max} [μHz]	$\Delta\nu$ [μHz]	$\Delta\Pi_1$ [s]	MClass [M_{\odot}]	MG17 [M_{\odot}]	MS16 [M_{\odot}]	MT18 [M_{\odot}]	L [L_{\odot}]
11775041	RC	34.14 ± 0.44	4.165 ± 0.004	248	1.26 ± 0.05	1.25 ± 0.05	1.23 ± 0.05	1.02 ± 0.07	70.1 ± 1.9
11820688	RC	38.78 ± 0.26	4.172 ± 0.002	282	1.69 ± 0.03	1.64 ± 0.03	1.63 ± 0.03	1.37 ± 0.08	66.8 ± 1.0
11913049	RC	28.39 ± 0.35	3.605 ± 0.003	241	1.12 ± 0.04	1.06 ± 0.04	1.02 ± 0.04	0.91 ± 0.06	51.9 ± 1.4
12056819	RGB	43.58 ± 0.29	4.606 ± 0.003	...	1.6 ± 0.03	1.37 ± 0.03	1.52 ± 0.03	1.3 ± 0.07	48.8 ± 0.8
12121207	RC	27.61 ± 0.18	3.627 ± 0.003	342	1.1 ± 0.02	1.06 ± 0.02	1.03 ± 0.02	0.89 ± 0.05	64.6 ± 1.0
12169845	RGB	30.9 ± 0.23	3.301 ± 0.002	...	2.07 ± 0.05	1.81 ± 0.04	1.98 ± 0.05	1.68 ± 0.09	82.0 ± 1.3
12316494	RC	31.09 ± 0.21	3.756 ± 0.003	255	1.37 ± 0.03	1.33 ± 0.03	1.31 ± 0.03	1.11 ± 0.06	73.0 ± 1.2

Note – The uncertainties of $\Delta\Pi_1$ are of the order of a few seconds. I did not determine $\Delta\Pi_1$ for RGB stars. The stellar masses were calculated with the scaling relations proposed by Kjeldsen and Bedding (1995) (MClass), Guggenberger et al. (2017) (MG17), Sharma et al. (2016) (MS16), and Themeßl et al. (2018) (MT18).

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